

Deliverable 3.3

Final report on Living Labs application and lessons learned

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Final report on Living Labs application and lessons learned

This report presents a synthesis of how RUSTIK’s Living Lab methodology was implemented and experienced across fourteen diverse Pilot Regions. Drawing on learning from practice, the report explores how place-based, collaborative experimentation supported regions to learn about and respond to socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital transitions in rural areas across Europe. It first outlines the conceptual and methodological foundations of Living Labs, then describes how RUSTIK adapted these principles to develop a structured, yet flexible, approach centred on co-design, data experimentation, and iterative learning. Experience from practical interventions in the Living Labs highlights the importance of contextual factors, including institutional capacity, data quality and maturity, and local stakeholder cohesion. An implementation typology reflecting common patterns across Living Labs is proposed. The report concludes with implications and recommendations for future rural Living Labs and for designing effective multi-actor, place-based innovation processes in rural areas.

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	DMP	Data management plan	

Dissemination level	PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	<u>X</u>
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

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Summary

Living Labs offer a **collaborative, place-based approach** that can be used to **support local policy and practice learning and experimentation**. In RUSTIK, fourteen Living Labs operated from 2023 to 2025 across diverse rural regions. Their shared purpose was to support rural actors in the Pilot Regions to navigate socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital transitions. Each Living Lab was jointly led by an academic partner (the Living Lab Co-ordinator) and a regional practice partner (the Pilot Region Partner). Working together, they convened stakeholders to work through three activity cycles:

1. Identifying a specific rural transition challenge for the region.
2. Designing and delivering a 'data experiment' to inform responses to the challenge.
3. Applying and sharing learning.

What RUSTIK Living Labs achieved

Living Labs established new collaborations and developed data experiments that provided practical evidence to support future strategies and decision-making in their regions. Several developed mapping tools, integrated datasets, or other analytical outputs that are informing policy discussions in and for rural areas. Others strengthened local networks and enhanced stakeholder confidence in using data to support transition planning.

What enabled success

Implementation varied across the fourteen Living Labs. They were most effective where:

- Institutional capacity and local networks were strong.
- Relevant data was available or could be feasibly generated.
- The Pilot Region Partner enjoyed the status of a trusted intermediary.
- The transition challenge selected aligned with existing policy priorities.
- Stakeholders could see a pathway from evidence to action.

In areas with limited organisational capacity, low stakeholder cohesion, low data maturity, and shifting political or organisational contexts, Living Labs' ambitions were constrained, requiring more foundational approaches.

Implications for policy and practice

RUSTIK demonstrates that Living Labs can provide structured frameworks for convening stakeholders, building shared understanding, and developing and refining actionable insights tailored to local challenges. Their value lies in **adapting the core principles of co-creation, experimentation, and iterative learning to the governance realities of rural areas**.

Living Labs can further help to reveal underlying issues for rural governance, such as coordination gaps and capacity challenges. They can be used not only as innovation platforms, but also to **identify practical constraints and develop recommendations for capacity-building**.

Living Labs' data experiments were limited by fragmented and inconsistent data, and some rural areas and organisations lacked even basic information. **Foundational actions** such as standardising datasets and improving spatial granularity are still needed.

Lessons for future Living Labs in rural development

1. **Start from governance realities.** Embedding Living Labs within existing strategies and institutional responsibilities creates clearer pathways for uptake and avoids ‘project only’ outcomes.
2. **Include a trusted intermediary.** An intermediary organisation that is trusted in the region is essential for building and maintaining engagement and translating outcomes.
3. **Match expectations to capacity.** In many rural areas, incremental improvements are more feasible and achievable than large-scale or radical transformations.
4. **Look for low-cost interventions.** Low-cost actions that are designed to deliver tangible benefits reduce the risk of political ambivalence and can be undertaken when political or funding changes occur.
5. **Plan early to enhance the sustainability of interventions.** Using results and maintaining relationships requires stewardship. Where Living Labs can integrate outputs into routine practice, longer-term value is more likely.

1. Introduction

Rural areas across Europe are experiencing significant socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital transitions. While these transitions are widely shared, different regions face distinct place-based challenges and opportunities that are shaped by their geographies, functions, resources, and other characteristics. RUSTIK aims to support rural communities and policymakers in developing strategies that respond to both shared and locally specific transition needs. This requires approaches that generate locally adapted knowledge and encourage collaboration between actors.

To meet this need, RUSTIK adopted the Living Lab methodology, which works to “design, test and learn from social and technical innovation in real time” (Marvin et al. 2018: 1). While the methodology originated in urban innovation settings, Living Labs have increasingly been established in rural development (e.g. Maye et al. 2021, Kallai 2020, Habibipour et al. 2021) because they offer a structured way to co-design practical solutions with those directly involved. Their central premise is that effective interventions must be developed and tested within real-world contexts, through the active participation of local actors.

RUSTIK established Living Labs in fourteen Pilot Regions. Pilot Regions represent the geographical and/or administrative areas in which project partners operate, while the Living Lab approach provided the framework for collaboration and experimentation. At the heart of each RUSTIK Living Lab was a ‘data experiment’: a small-scale, novel attempt to use data, tools, or methods to generate actionable insights on a transition challenge for the region. These experiments were designed to both support local decision-making and to provide examples and inspiration with wider relevance for other rural areas or policies at larger scales.

From early 2023 to late 2025, RUSTIK Living Labs moved through three activity cycles:

1. Identifying a specific rural transition challenge for the region.
2. Designing and delivering a data experiment to inform responses to the challenge.
3. Applying and sharing learning.

This report draws on experiences and learning from all three cycles to examine how Living Labs were implemented in diverse rural contexts and to reflect on the value of such approaches for supporting transitions in rural areas.

1.1. About this Deliverable

1.1.1. What the Deliverable does

This report provides a synthesis of how RUSTIK’s Living Lab methodology was developed and implemented across the fourteen Pilot Regions. It has four core purposes:

- Describing the RUSTIK Living Lab methodology.
- Bringing together practical insights from implementing the methodology across the consortium.
- Identifying cross-cutting themes from these experiences.

- Reflecting on the broader implications for future Living Lab applications in rural development.

The report is not a formal evaluation of the methodology, and it does not assess the quality, success, or technical robustness of individual Living Labs or data experiments. It also does not reproduce detailed methodological procedures or results, which can be found in other RUSTIK Deliverables (see below). Rather, the focus is on generalisable learning about the Living Lab methodology within RUSTIK, how it functioned in diverse rural contexts, and what insights may be transferable to future initiatives.

Finally, at the time of writing, RUSTIK Living Labs are still finalising activities in their regions, including disseminating results and establishing future collaborations. The report cannot make claims about the longer-term outcomes or impacts of this ongoing work.

1.1.2. How the Deliverable was produced

To situate the RUSTIK methodology, the report draws on an interpretive review of the scientific literature on Living Labs and policy and practice experimentation. This literature was initially compiled during the development of RUSTIK’s methodology and has been updated for this report.

In exploring implementation in practice, the report draws upon evidence generated throughout RUSTIK Living Labs’ operational period. Specifically:

- Reports from individual Living Labs submitted during Cycles 1, 2, and 3 were analysed to identify common themes and key differences, as well as reflections on implementation.
- Internal project documentation, including methodological guidance and materials from joint Living Lab meetings were reviewed to understand how the Living Lab methodology was interpreted and adapted across the project.
- Twenty-seven semi-structured interviews were conducted with academic and practice partners from the Living Labs in autumn 2025, providing in-depth perspectives on the methodology and reflections from experience.

Findings from these three streams were compared across Living Labs to identify shared patterns and contextual drivers. This synthesis process informed both the cross-cutting lessons and implementation typology presented in the later sections of the report.

1.1.3. How the Deliverable relates to other RUSTIK Deliverables

Living Labs were a cornerstone of RUSTIK’s overall approach, and this report is one of several that describe and discuss aspects of this work. It focuses on how the Living Lab methodology functioned in practice. It does not provide details of regional contexts, full documentation of Living Lab activities, technical results of data experiments, or a synthesis of transition pathways. Readers seeking more information on these aspects should consult the Deliverables listed in Table 1, which are available on the RUSTIK website.

Table 1: List of related RUSTIK Deliverables

Further information	Relevant deliverable/s
Context on the functional characteristics of Pilot Regions and how they face transitions.	D1.2 <i>Synthesis of the 14 Pilot Regions’ Reports</i> (2023)

Further information	Relevant deliverable/s
A comparative overview of data needs and resources in each Pilot Region	D2.2 Comparative analysis of Living Lab data needs investigations (2023)
Detailed Cycle 1 findings, including transition challenges identified by each Living Lab	D3.1 Reports of Pilot Regions' audits on data use and needs and transition policy challenges and opportunities (2023)
Full details of Cycle 2 data experiments, including methods and preliminary results	D3.2 Reports of results of 14 Pilot Regions' experiments (2024)
Insights on governance structures and institutional capacity to respond to transition challenges	D4.2 Report on the institutional structures and policy panoramas in the Pilot Regions (2024)
Analysis of transition pathways using Living Lab findings	D5.1 Report on the analysis of the Living Lab reports and findings on transition pathways (forthcoming)
Technical synthesis of data tools, analytical approaches, and methods trialed in the experiments	D5.2 Collection of data analysis tools and assessment approaches (forthcoming)

Figure 1 shows a visual representation of the links between the deliverables, including how D3.3. will inform the upcoming analysis of the Living Labs' outcomes in WP5.

After the project ends, we envisage continued reciprocal relationships between the work completed in these WPs, with the conclusions of WP5 continuing to conceptually reinforce WP1, WP2 and WP4.

Figure 1: The relationship between the RUSTIK Work Packages, the Deliverables used to inform this report, and the WP5 Deliverables that will report on the final Living Lab results

1.2. Structure and reader guide

This report is structured to move from the conceptual and methodological foundations of Living Labs to RUSTIK’s methodology and the experiences of implementing this approach across the 14 Living Labs. This structure serves to explain how Living Labs were applied to strengthen data collection and interpretation in support of rural transitions across the RUSTIK consortium. Together, these sections provide a coherent narrative that can be read as a whole.

For readers who have specific roles or interests, Table 2 provides shorter, focused reading pathways.

Table 2: Recommended reader pathways

Reader	Recommended sections
Researchers needing to understand Living Lab theory and methodological contribution.	Section 2 (theoretical background); Section 3 (methodological rationale, key features)
Future project organisers seeking to learn how the methodology worked in practice.	Section 4 (operationalisation); Section 5 (reflections); Section 6 (Synthesis) Conclusion
Facilitators interested in stakeholder engagement.	Section 5 (reflections)
Policy audiences seeking a briefing.	Summary; Sections 6.1-6.4 (synthesised lessons); Conclusion.
Technical readers interested in data experiments	Section 3.4 (methodology); Section 4.2.2 (implementation), 6.2 (synthesised lessons)

2. Living Labs: Conceptual and methodological foundations

This technical section covers the conceptual and methodological grounding for understanding the Living Lab approach. Drawing on the scientific literature, it outlines how the broader family of ‘lab’ approaches in policy and practice has developed as a form of collaborative, real-world experimentation and how these approaches relate to wider traditions of co-production and place-based innovation. It identifies the key characteristics and limitations identified in previous research and highlights the relevance of Living Labs for rural development. These conceptual foundations provide a framework for interpreting how Living Labs function within RUSTIK (Section 3) and the assumptions behind their use.

2.1. Conceptualising ‘labs’ in policy and practice

Laboratories, or labs, have long been associated with scientists in white coats, conducting precise experiments in carefully controlled conditions. More recently, lab terminology has proliferated outside this classic context (Williamson 2015, Scholl & Kemp 2016, Voytenko et al. 2016). In policy and practice contexts, labs have become conceptualised as taking an **experimental approach to tackling societal challenges**, often as part of collaborative initiatives for “designing the future” (Williamson 2015: 260). However, there is no consistently agreed-upon definition of what constitutes a lab in such contexts, nor of the extent to which lab approaches function as explicit methodologies rather than more general orientations or ways of working.

Several trends have influenced the emergence of labs for policy and practice contexts, including:

- Increasing awareness of climate change and action for **sustainability transitions** (e.g. Bulkeley & Castán Broto 2013, Sengers et al. 2020, von Wirth et al. 2019).
- A growing **place-based and polycentric** policy agenda (Huitema et al. 2018).
- The possibilities offered by **digitalisation** and ‘big data’ (e.g. Acevedo & Dassen 2016, Williamson 2015).
- The rise of **public sector innovation** (Lewis et al. 2019).
- New emphasis on the **co-production** of policy solutions (McGann et al. 2021, Osborne et al. 2016).
- An **‘experimentalist turn’** in governance (Bulkeley et al. 2016, Zeitlin 2016) and the social sciences (Huitema et al. 2018).

In policy and practice, labs are viewed as providing a potential way to address societal challenges by including new actors and decentralising control (Sengers et al. 2020, Torrens & von Wirth 2021) and encouraging experimentation through diverse forms of intervention (Smeds & Acuto 2018). Experimentation in a policy sense is viewed as providing “a way of reframing policy issues and generating and testing new solutions to public problems” (Lewis et al. 2019: 2). Labs have hence been envisaged as platforms for collaboration (Voytenko et al. 2016) that enable governance to work creatively, rather than procedurally (Scholl & Kemp 2016).

These labs are known by a variety of terms, including “Living Labs” (Voytenko et al. 2016), “public sector innovation labs” (Acevedo & Dassen 2016, Lewis et al. 2020), “transition labs” (Nevens et al. 2013), and “city”, “urban”, or “civic” labs that engage residents as stakeholders (Aernouts et

al 2020, Scholl & Kemp 2016). They have a variety of goals and ways of working, and there is limited consensus on how to define them (Scholl & Kemp 2016, Voytenko 2016). However, some common characteristics can be identified:

- **Embeddedness:** labs are typically embedded in a geographical area (Voytenko et al. 2016) or situated in a particular policy or innovation context (Torrens & von Wirth 2021).
- **Hybridity and boundary crossing:** labs bridge governance and society (McGann et al. 2021, Scholl & Kemp 2016) and bring cross-sectoral (Williamson 2015) or multi-disciplinary (Scholl & Kemp 2016) perspectives to complex problems.
- **Stakeholder participation:** labs incorporate multiple stakeholders (Scholl & Kemp 2016) and often encourage user involvement in decision-making (Acevedo & Dassen 2016, Voytenko et al. 2016). They may take a facilitation role (McGann et al. 2021) or foster forms of local empowerment (Bulkeley et al. 2016) through participatory action (Veeckman & van der Graaf 2015).
- **Diverse methods:** labs draw on a range of methods and techniques for co-creation (Scholl & Kemp 2016) and often require a flexible use of resources and tools (Acevedo & Dassen 2016).
- **Experimentation:** labs are explicitly experimental (Voytenko et al. 2016), often favouring low-cost experimentation (Acevedo & Dassen 2016).
- **Learning:** labs operate as learning environments (Scholl & Kemp 2016, Voytenko et al. 2016) and are often organised with specific learning objectives in mind (Torrens & von Wirth 2021).

2.2. Living Labs

Living Labs – the methodology adopted by RUSTIK – aim to “**allow stakeholders to design, test and learn from socio-technical innovations in real time**” (von Wirth et al. 2019: 30). They can be understood as **both an arena and an approach** (Voytenko et al. 2016). As an **arena**, Living Labs are “geographically embedded in real places” (Voytenko et al. 2016: 46). They may be convened by national or regional authorities, municipalities and local actors, or smaller community groups (Bulkeley et al. 2018).

As an **approach**, Living Labs involve “intentional collaborative experimentation” (Voytenko et al. 2016: 46). Experiments in this sense are “real-world interventions” (Torrens & von Wirth 2021:4). As Living Lab experiments are co-designed with stakeholders, the exact purpose for each experiment will vary. They have a **practical purpose** that “respond[s] to a particular problem” (Karvonen 2018: 203) or investigates a specific solution in place. Some Living Labs are more realistic than others (Fuglsang et al. 2021). For example, some turn real-life settings into experimental sites, while others create testbeds where risks can be more safely managed.

Sustainability and transitions are often key topics for Living Labs. For example, some have explored sustainable development through ‘smart city’ initiatives (Leminen et al. 2017), while others have developed innovation activities to improve everyday sustainability (Nyström et al., 2014). Living Labs can empower local actors and distribute responsibility for finding more sustainable solutions. They also promote cultural change in how people work together by shifting the focus from hierarchical decision-making to deliberative, shared solutions and their application in real-life settings (Forbat et al. 2025).

2.3. Conceptualising ‘experiments’

The classic meaning of ‘experiment’ in a scientific laboratory refers to an intervention where conditions are controlled to isolate an effect, with the aim of developing empirical knowledge about the material world. By contrast, experiments in policy and practice contexts are typically “**real-world interventions**” (Torrens & von Wirth 2021: 4) where researchers are participants rather than simply observers (Evans 2011). Policy and practice experiments appear in the literature through four common viewpoints:

- Experiments as **governance** (e.g. Sengers et al. 2019, Torrens & von Wirth 2021), which work to reconfigure governance capacities, resources, and actors (von Wirth et al. 2019) by creating new partnerships and collaborative forms of planning (Ehnert 2023). This view of experimentation involves networked governance (Lewis et al. 2019, Williamson 2015) and distributed, plural policy approaches (McGann et al. 2021).
- Experiments as **methods** (e.g. Lewis et al. 2019, Huitema et al. 2018), working through “collective search and exploration processes” (von Wirth et al. 2019: 231). This view of experimentation attends to the tools, frameworks, and capabilities needed to design and conduct experimentation.
- Experiments as **strategic intervention** and **practical problem-solving** (e.g. Ansell & Bartenberger 2016, Smeds & Acuto 2018), which work to identify “alternative options for how ... action can be brought to bear on an identified problem” (Howlett 2014: 192). This view of experimentation rests on deconstructing problems (Lewis et al. 2019) and envisioning desirable futures (Williamson 2015).
- Experiments as developing **niches** (e.g. Sengers et al. 2019) by creating relatively protected spaces where innovation can develop and potentially ‘break through’ into the mainstream (Bulkeley & Castán Broto 2013, Ehnert 2023). This view of experimentation often focuses on promoting emergent practices that have the potential to spark future change (Savini & Bertolini 2019).

How an experiment in a real-world setting should be defined continues to be debated in the literature. For example, Ansell & Bartenberger (2016: 65) define an experiment simply as a “**novel attempt to solve a problem**”. By contrast, Sengers et al. (2019: 161) offer a more complex definition of an experiment as “**an inclusive, practice-based and challenge-led initiative designed to promote system innovation through social learning**”. Some go further, arguing that experiments should be explicitly radical and transformative (e.g. Nevens et al. 2013).

These definitional differences partly emerge because the experimentalist turn in policy and practice carries a wide range of expectations, including diffusing policies; changing political structures; creating new opportunities; effecting socio-technical transformations; and facilitating the work of knowing, managing, and governing (Bulkeley & Castán Broto 2013). Unfortunately, diverse expectations and vague definitions can lead to the term ‘experiment’ being used to simply describe “anything that deviates from normality” (Huitema et al. 2018: 145).

Karvonen (2018) argues that a useful language of policy and practice experimentation must do more than describe divergence from the status quo. Rather, experiments should be purposeful, and “develop knowledge to respond to a particular problem” (Karvonen 2018: 203). The concept of **purposive experimentation** (Bulkeley & Castán Broto 2013, von Wirth et al. 2019) has

particularly emerged through the transitions literature (Sengers et al. 2019). For Bulkeley et al. (2019: 318), such experimentation “**provides a means by which diverse actors seek to navigate and make sense of the present whilst also giving concrete form to particular visions of the future**”. This can include, for example, testing or establishing good practice, supporting or contesting existing knowledge claims (Bulkeley & Castán Broto 2013), and demonstrating the need for change (Voytenko et al. 2016, Huitema et al. 2018). Policy and practice experimentation can thereby help translate “long-term visions and socio-technical pathways into more short-term and concrete action and practices” (von Wirth et al. 2019: 231).

In their intervention in the debate, Caniglia et al. (2017) argue that the term ‘experiment’ is appropriate where there is an **intervention** – an action that induces change – and the intervention produces **empirical evidence**. Their distinction between **experiments on problems and experiments on solutions** adds helpful detail here, as Table 3 outlines.

Table 3: Experiments on problems and solutions (adapted from Caniglia et al. 2017)

Experiments on problems	Experiments on solutions
Aim: to produce evidence about existing challenges and their causes.	Aim: to produce evidence about potential solutions or opportunities.
Key questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ How and why are things as they are? ➔ What features does the challenge have? ➔ Is the perceived challenge really the issue? 	Key questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ How can a new intervention be designed? ➔ What action can be taken, and will it work? ➔ Which potential solutions are preferable?
Generate analytical causal knowledge .	Generate actionable knowledge .

2.4. Learning from experimentation

Learning is understood in the literature as one of the key purposes of experimentation (Mukhtar-Landgren et al. 2019, Voytenko et al. 2016), and choosing experiments for a specific purpose can help stakeholders learn about issues they are interested in (Scholl & Kemp 2016). While these experiences are often described as learning by doing (e.g. Bulkeley et al. 2016), some caution that learning should be “explicitly specified and directed” (Voytenko et al. 2016: 47) or formalised through feedback loops (Karvonen 2018) rather than presumed to occur or treated as a side-effect. Importantly, experiments provide “**room to fail**” (Scholl & Kemp 2016: 92). Every experiment carries the possibility that ideas may not work or that outcomes may diverge from expectations, and this potential for failure is widely recognised as a central opportunity for learning.

Ansell and Bartenberger (2016) identify three logics for learning through experimentation, which are summarised in the table below.

Table 4: Three logics for learning from experimentation (adapted from Ansell & Bartenberger 2016).

Logic	Learning interest	Operationalisation
Controlled	Using experiments to explore a hypothesis and learn about cause and effect.	Designing interventions and controlling variables.
Parallel	Using multiple experiments to learn from trial and error.	Creating conditions for variation and embracing failure.
Generative	Using experiments to generate and refine solutions.	Iterative feedback, reflection, and refinement.

2.5. Impact and outcomes

There are differing perspectives on the impact and outcomes that Living Labs should generate. Some argue that co-production is “intrinsically valuable as a *process* regardless of the quality or effectiveness of the outputs produced” (McGann et al. 2021: 302, original emphasis). Others consider that experiments should be undertaken to inform outcomes beyond the scope of the experiment itself. Sengers et al. (2020: 1150) observe that “it is largely assumed that the proliferation of empowering local initiatives will (...) ‘add up’ to broader systemic change” but argue that the processes through which this change is intended to occur are under-theorised. They call attention to the need to **consider what happens *beyond* the experiment in three ways:**

- **Temporal** outcomes concern impact over time, after the experiment ends.
- **Spatial** outcomes create impact in other spatial contexts, beyond the Living Lab arena.
- **Structural** outcomes contribute towards addressing a challenge or pursuing an opportunity.

Since a successful experiment will ideally lead to new ideas or practices being adopted, impact can also be viewed through an **innovation lens**. The ways this could occur, and the strategies noted in the literature to help build impact (e.g. von Wirth et al. 2019, Sengers et al. 2020, Smeds & Acuto 2018) are summarised in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Types of impact identified in the literature (adapted from von Wirth et al. 2019, Sengers et al. 2020, Smeds & Acuto 2018)

Mechanism	Outcomes	Impact strategies
Embedding	The design or outcomes from an experiment are adopted or integrated into existing local structures or networks.	→ Place-making → Consolidation → Activating network partners
Diffusion	Elements of the experiment are shared and reproduced through horizontal ‘scaling out’.	→ Replication → Dissemination
Scaling	The experiment becomes bigger in content or remit through vertical ‘scaling up’.	→ Expansion → Resourcing

Studies suggest that labs are more likely to have impactful outcomes when they:

- Cohere and participate in effective networks (Bulkeley et al. 2016, Acevedo & Dassen 2016).
- Develop shared meaning and coherent visions (Nevens et al. 2013, Acevedo & Dassen 2016).
- Have strategic learning goals (Scholl & Kemp 2016).
- Have a degree of change agency and can enact improvement (McGann et al. 2021, Bulkeley et al. 2018).
- Involve governance partners in configuring the lab and designing activities (Scholl & Kemp 2016).
- Imply a manageable scale of change and actor coordination (Smeds & Acuto 2018).

2.6. Challenges and critiques

Scholars point out that the ability of labs to make a practical contribution and effectively realise their ambitions depends heavily on how they are operationalised (e.g. Lewis et al. 2019, Voytenko et al. 2016). The following challenges are identified in the literature:

- **Capacity** challenges concern the ability of labs and experiments to address the issues that matter for governance agendas (Acevedo & Dassen 2016). This includes the time and cost of co-designing solutions (McGann et al. 2021) and the resources needed to effect change (von Wirth et al. 2019).
- **Sustainability** challenges concern the ability of labs and experiments to create solutions that are sustainable over time. This includes the funding landscape (Torrens & von Wirth 2021) and the risk of changing political priorities (McGann et al. 2021).
- **Impact** challenges concern the ability of labs and experiments to catalyse change (Lewis et al. 2019, Nevens et al. 2013). Such challenges can include the small size of many labs (Lewis et al. 2019), their ambition in experimenting (Smeds & Acuto 2018), and the extent to which evidence from experiments is likely to be a consideration for governance decision-makers (Huitema et al. 2018).

For Sengers et al. (2019: 161), “experimentation is mostly perceived as something positive, [but] its profusion should not be uncritically hailed as a sure blessing”. The challenges mentioned above partly explain why this is the case. More generally, the experimental space is always constrained by the bounds of what can or cannot happen within it (Evans 2011). As von Wirth et al. (2019: 231) complain, celebrating the specificity of place-based initiatives “runs the risk of treating each and every experiment as idiosyncratic with little scope nor insight about which lessons can be drawn (...) and applied more broadly”.

However, some scholars question whether experimentation can realistically have results in challenging and complex contexts (McGann et al. 2021). Transitions are particularly challenging to influence because, while short- and medium-term actions are required, transitions themselves occur over the long-term (Nevens et al. 2013). Relatedly, Torrens & von Wirth (2021: 9) critique the tendency of experiments to produce an “unambitious incrementalism” that privileges the “achievable over the necessary”. Some of the strongest critics of experimentation argue that “sanctioned optimism” risks replacing real reform with “reactive localism” (Evans 2011: 232).

Moreover, experimentation is not a neutral activity. Experiments can have both positive and negative implications (Torrens & von Wirth 2021), and, although learning from failure is often emphasised, failure can also have adverse impacts when intended outcomes are not delivered. While some may gain benefits from labs and experimentation, others may bear costs (Huitema et al. 2018). Savini and Bertolini (2019) hence critique what they view as a lack of reflection on the political logics behind experimentation, and the specific institutional conditions that determine how experiments are identified and promoted. Bulkeley and Castán Broto (2013) similarly ask the critical question: *who gets to decide?*

2.7. Concluding remarks

The conceptual and methodological literature on Living Labs highlights some recurring themes, including: the importance of real-world experimentation, the role of multi-actor collaboration, the need for iterative learning, and the influence of contextual constraints on Living Labs' achievements. The literature also points to known challenges, such as capacity limitations, concerns about longer-term sustainability, and the risk of over-claiming impact.

These insights provide important grounding for understanding the approach taken in RUSTIK and the factors that shaped implementation. They help illustrate why RUSTIK selected Living Labs as an appropriate methodology for addressing transitions in rural areas, which is discussed further in the following section. At the same time, insights from the literature emphasise the need for Living Labs to be locally embedded and incorporate flexibility and adaptation. This reinforces that Living Labs cannot be treated as a uniform model that, when implemented across multiple places, delivers consistent and comparable results. Instead, the form and feasibility of each Living Lab depend on its local context and the mix of capacities and participatory dynamics involved.

This understanding directly informs the methodological choices that Section 3 describes. The next section explains how RUSTIK interpreted the Living Lab approach for diverse rural areas and how the concept of a data experiment was developed. In moving from theory to design, Section 3 thereby translates the broad principles discussed here into the specific framework for RUSTIK's fourteen Living Labs.

3. RUSTIK's Living Lab methodology

This section sets out how the Living Lab methodology was interpreted and operationalised within RUSTIK. Building on the conceptual foundations outlined in Section 2, the section explains the rationale for adopting a Living Lab approach, the core features that structured RUSTIK's methodology, and the process developed to guide implementation across the fourteen Pilot Regions. The section also outlines how experimentation was specifically translated into a concept of data experiments. These elements provide the methodological architecture behind RUSTIK's collaborative, place-based work with regional partners and rural stakeholders.

3.1. Rationale for using Living Labs in RUSTIK

The Living Lab methodology was originally developed in urban settings, and its application to rural contexts has emerged more recently (e.g. Maye et al. 2021, Habibipour et al., 2021, Ali et al., 2025). These applications reflect methodological developments, with Living Labs shifting from a primary focus on technological developments to interdisciplinary perspectives on sustainable development, including socio-economic and environmental change (Zavratnik et al., 2019).

RUSTIK adopted the Living Lab methodology because it offers a structured yet flexible approach for generating locally grounded, actionable knowledge in diverse rural areas. RUSTIK Living Labs were designed to bring research and practice partners together, working with regional stakeholders to:

- Explore how the Pilot Region is **navigating socio-economic, climate/environmental and digital transitions** and create a shared vision for a resilient, sustainable future.
- Identify how **new data, methods, and tools** could provide knowledge about the region to help design better transition strategies.
- Test **how this works in practice**.
- **Co-design actions, strategies, and/or improved policy frameworks** for rural decision-makers, to work towards their shared vision for the future.

Within RUSTIK, Living Labs address transitions by enabling regional actors to co-design, test, and learn from new ideas in real-world contexts. RUSTIK Living Labs therefore serve both as a **collaborative framework** for stakeholder engagement and as a **methodological driver** for innovation.

3.2. Key features of RUSTIK Living Labs

RUSTIK Living Labs are based on the five key operational characteristics identified by Voytenko et al. (2016):

1. **Geographical embeddedness:** the Living Lab is place-based and works within a specific geographical area or administrative unit.
2. **Leadership and ownership:** the Living Lab has clear leadership to help coordinate, clarify, and pursue shared objectives.

3. **Participation and user involvement:** the Living Lab uses cross-sector participation and involves end users and beneficiaries.
4. **Experimentation and learning:** the Living Lab experiments with new approaches, data, tools, and methods to learn what works in practice.
5. **Evaluation and refinement:** Living Lab leadership and participants regularly reflect on what they are achieving and use this learning to refine their goals and ways of working over time.

3.2.1. Geographical embeddedness

RUSTIK has 14 participating Pilot Regions, each of which operates a Living Lab. Each Pilot Region reflects a defined geographical area. In most cases, this geography corresponds to the administrative area for the Pilot Region Partner, but there are some differences.

Table 6: List of Pilot Regions, partners, and Living Lab geographies. Adapted from D1.2.

Pilot Region	Pilot Region Partner type	Living Lab geography
Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT)	Regional development agency and Local Action Group (LAG)	A group of 17 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a LAG. Pop. 52,451.
Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG)	LAG	A group of 3 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a LAG. Pop. 35,815.
North Karelia (FI)	Regional authority	NUTS3 region comprising 13 municipalities. Pop. 163,281.
Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)	Regional authority and LAG	NUTS3 region comprising 137 municipalities. Pop. 103,767
Garfagnana (IT)	LAG	A group of 35 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a LAG. Pop. 87,585.
Parma, Piacenza & Ferrara (IT)	Interbranch organisation (sector body)	NUTS3 region comprising 127 municipalities. Pop. 1,071,974.
Woj. Mazowieckie (PL) – Szydłowiecki powiat	National rural development foundation.	A group of 5 municipalities at LAU2 level. Pop. 40,000.
Woj. Świętokrzyskie (PL)	Regional university.	NUTS2 region. Pop. 1,187,693.
Zaječar District (RS)	Regional development agency.	NUTS3 region comprising 4 municipalities. Pop. 97,778.
Osrednjeslovenska (SI)	Regional cooperative organisation.	NUTS3 region comprising 25 municipalities. Pop. 555,293.
Galicia (ES) – model villages	Regional development agency.	Non-contiguous group of 20 LAU2 municipalities. Pop. 40,652.
Gloucestershire (UK)	County-level rural development organisation	Group of 4 rural districts at LAU2 level. Pop. 397,824.
Monmouthshire (UK)	County council	Single county at NUTS3 level. Pop. 93,000.

3.2.2. Leadership and ownership

Each RUSTIK Living Lab was jointly led by a Living Lab Coordinator and a Pilot Region Partner. The **Living Lab Coordinator** represented an academic partner and was responsible for operationalising RUSTIK's Living Lab methodology and documenting progress. They had a dual role as a researcher for RUSTIK and a facilitator supporting the Pilot Region Partner. They hence provided a critical link between needs and experience in the Pilot Region and requirements at the project level.

The **Pilot Region Partner** was a practice partner from a local or regional authority, LAG, regional development agency, NGO, or business association (Table 6). In one case, the Pilot Region Partner represented a small local university. Pilot Region Partners brought local knowledge, experience, and networks to the Living Lab and took a key role in identifying the Living Lab's focus on relevant transition challenges. They also held and managed an additional budget for subcontracting additional data expertise, if required.

RUSTIK's approach to including Pilot Region Partners as co-leads was informed by previous research identifying five roles for municipalities in governance experiments (Eneqvist & Karvonen 2021):

- **Visioning:** framing values, norms, and perceptions; deciding on a vision for a desired future.
- **Facilitating:** facilitating engagement and interactions between stakeholders.
- **Supporting:** provisioning and assisting experiments.
- **Amplifying:** upscaling and replicating results.
- **Guarding:** protecting public values and ensuring that experiments address the most relevant issues.

3.2.3. Participation and user involvement

As a core principle for RUSTIK Living Labs, participation shaped not only who was involved but also how knowledge was generated and used. A multi-actor, participatory approach aimed to support the relevance and legitimacy of Living Labs and the usability of their findings.

In practice, this meant that relevant local stakeholders were invited to contribute at multiple points across the Living Lab cycles. Their involvement supported both the co-design of activities and the practical grounding of the Living Lab's work and results in local realities. Stakeholders contributed to:

- Defining Living Lab objectives and refining them over time as understanding of the transition challenge evolved.
- Discussing and adapting practical methods and processes for operating the Living Lab.
- Identifying opportunities to gather, test, and use data in the Pilot Region.
- Developing data collection instruments and, in some cases, directly participating in data collection.
- Reflecting on progress, validating emerging findings, and sharing learning from Living Lab activities.
- Contributing to the formulation of policy and practice recommendations at regional and wider scales.

3.2.4. Experimentation and learning

RUSTIK adopted the basic definition of an experiment as a “**novel attempt to solve a problem**” (Ansell & Bartenberger 2016: 65). In RUSTIK, this was understood as:

1. Experimentation related to a real and relevant **transition challenge** (or opportunity) within the Pilot Region.
2. The experiment tried a **novel data source, method, or tool** to address the challenge.
3. The experiment had the potential to **inform practical progress** towards responding to the challenge.
4. It was recognised that the experiment might not work as hoped, but that there would be opportunities to **learn from failure**.

RUSTIK recognised that learning in a Living Lab context differs from learning as it may be understood in an academic teaching or research dissemination context. In a Living Lab, stakeholders need to agree that the results from an experiment will have practical relevance. To learn effectively within a RUSTIK Living Lab, it was recognised that:

- The outcomes from Living Lab activities and the data experiment should be informative.
- The key assumptions should be explicitly articulated.
- What counts for success – and how the Living Lab will know what does not work – should be discussed and understood in advance.

RUSTIK data experiments are elaborated in more detail in Section 3.4. below.

3.2.5. Evaluation and refinement

Evaluation in RUSTIK Living Labs was intended as a continuous, formative process. In each activity Cycle (see Section 3.3 below), Living Labs followed a four-step process designed to create feedback loops and provide opportunities for reflection and self-evaluation. The steps were:

1. Define the focus for activities during the cycle and envision the immediate goals and outcomes for the Living Lab.
2. Identify, plan, and co-design the activities for the cycle.
3. Implement the activities and test ideas.
4. Evaluate the outcomes of the activities and reflect on experiences from the cycle.

The evaluative step informed the refinement of subsequent cycles, and Living Lab report templates included prompts to record reflections. Reflections were used to adjust objectives, adapt methods, and revisit assumptions. In this way, self-evaluation functioned to support learning and adaptation rather than performance measurement, supporting iterative improvement across the operational period.

3.3. Operationalisation

Following a preparation phase at the beginning of the project, the operational period for RUSTIK Living Labs was divided into three main activity cycles (Figure 2). **Cycle 1** focused on planning possibilities for better action to address transitions in the Pilot Region. During this cycle, each Living Lab undertook activities to identify a specific **transition challenge** to focus its work on. The results of this cycle are available in *Deliverable 3.1: Reports of Pilot Regions audits on data use and needs and transition policy challenges and opportunities*.

During **Cycle 2**, Living Labs collaboratively designed and implemented a **data experiment** to address the transition challenge that they had identified. The experiments and preliminary results from this cycle are described in *Deliverable 3.2: Reports of results of 14 Pilot Regions experiments*. The full data experiment results will be synthesised in *Deliverable 5.1: Report on the analysis of the Living Lab reports and findings on transition pathways*. The data and tools used will be further discussed in the upcoming *Deliverable 5.2: Collection of data analysis tools and assessment approaches*.

Cycle 3 focused on **policy and practice learning** from the data experiments and from Living Lab activities more broadly. In addition to learning within Living Labs and dissemination activities, Cycle 3 also informs the upcoming *Deliverable 4.3: Report on place-based policies in the Pilot regions and a local perspective on Rural Proofing* and *Deliverable 5.1: Report on the analysis of the Living Lab reports and findings on transition pathways*.

Figure 2: RUSTIK Living Lab activity cycles

It is important to note that the RUSTIK project continued after the operational phase of the Living Labs concluded. As explained in the introduction, this report cannot, therefore, make claims about the longer-term outcomes or impacts of this ongoing work.

3.4. Data experiments

Within RUSTIK Living Labs, the concept of data experiments was developed to deliver two of the key objectives for Work Package 3:

1. To **evaluate, test, and refine enhanced methods for sourcing, using, and collating relevant data, information, and analytical approaches** that help better understand and support the needs of rural areas to address transition challenges.
2. To **analyse how best policy and data platforms, tools, and resources can support local actors and generate lessons** to inform:
 - a. Future regional, national, and EU policies; and,
 - b. Regional, national, and EU data resources/indicators and monitoring requirements.

Data experiments were at the core of Cycle 2. A RUSTIK data experiment required a **data source, tool, or method** (or a combination of these) that was new to the specific transition challenge identified within the Pilot Region. This could include:

- Using a new source of data or a new combination of existing sources.

- Using a new method to collect or analyse data.
- Using a new tool to collect or analyse data.

'New' in this sense was highly dependent on each Pilot Region's context and the needs identified during Living Lab Cycle 1.

3.4.1. Data experiment rationale and conceptualisation

RUSTIK data experiments were developed in recognition that raw data alone is of limited value. To become meaningful, any form of data needs to be **processed, organised, and interpreted**. This is expressed by the **information hierarchy** (Figure 3, below).

Figure 3: The information hierarchy (adapted from Rowley 2007).

For researchers, turning data into information can be a valued goal in and of itself. From the policy perspective, data is most useful once it provides **actionable knowledge**. For example, weather observations can be organised to produce information about a region's climate; if that information shows a trend to hotter and drier summers, the regional government can act to reduce water consumption or secure supply.

The data analytics literature provides useful insights on how data can be applied to generate actionable knowledge. This highlights four main potential 'tasks' for data (e.g. Lepenioti et al. 2020):

- **Describe:** using data to understand *what* has already happened.
- **Diagnose:** using data to explore or evaluate *why* something has happened.
- **Predict:** using data to examine what is likely to happen in the future.
- **Prescribe:** using data to determine what should be done in the future.

3.4.2. Data experiment design framework

To meet RUSTIK's ambitions, each proposed data experiment was expected to be able to positively answer five key questions:

1. Is it an **experiment**?
2. Is it **achievable**?
3. Is it **actionable**?
4. Is it **innovative**?
5. Is it **impactful**?

Table 7 outlines the criteria for each key question in the framework. Living Labs were provided with these questions and asked to complete a template prior to commencing their data experiments. The Work Package 3 coordinators met with each Living Lab team to discuss these templates and ensure the data experiment proposals met the project requirements.

Table 7: RUSTIK Data experiment design framework

Question	Core criteria	But not
<p>Is it an experiment? <i>Are we testing a data source, tool, or method and can we know whether it works?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ A data source, tool or method is being tested and/or piloted. ✓ The test is of practical relevance to the Living Lab's challenge or opportunity. ✓ There are explicit assumptions about what the data, tool, or method will do that can be proven or disproven. ✓ Whether the test/pilot 'works' can be answered at the end. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ General or typical research data collection. ✗ Data is primarily a by-product. ✗ Unspecified or irrelevant success criteria. ✗ Something that would happen anyway.
<p>Is it achievable? <i>Can we realistically do the experiment by the end of Cycle 2?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The experiment can be practically implemented during Cycle 2. ✓ There will be at minimum preliminary results to report at the end of Cycle 2. ✓ Living Lab partners have the capacity to deliver the experiment and/or can access necessary training and/or subcontract expertise. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Long time horizon. ✗ Preliminary results will not be able to explain whether the experiment 'worked'. ✗ Necessary skills and resources not available.
<p>Is it actionable? <i>Are Living Lab stakeholders likely to act on the results?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Outcomes from the experiment will be useful and informative for the Pilot Region Partner and Living Lab stakeholders. ✓ Practical actions can be envisaged as a result. ✓ These actions are realistic. ✓ The evidence will be sufficient for the expected action. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Solely descriptive results. ✗ Anticipated recommendations the Pilot Region Partner or stakeholders are unlikely or unable to pursue. ✗ High likelihood of no positive action. ✗ Insufficiently robust evidence to validate the action.
<p>Is it innovative? <i>Will RUSTIK's audiences see the experiment as something new?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The data source, tool, or method is new to the transition challenge context. ✓ Living Lab stakeholders agree that the experiment offers a new approach. ✓ RUSTIK's target audiences are likely to view the experiment as innovative. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Data sources, tools, or methods typically applied to the context. ✗ Data sources, tools, or methods only novel at a small scale. ✗ Simply using the word 'innovative'.

Question	Core criteria	But not
<p>Is it impactful? <i>Is there potential for the data, tool, or method to be adopted or replicated?</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ There is future potential for the experiment to be embedded in the region, <i>and/or</i> ✓ Diffused to other regions and adapted or replicated, <i>and/or</i> ✓ Scaled up nationally or internationally. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Nothing further is likely to happen following the experiment. ✗ Future potential is non-existent or highly speculative.

4. Implementation

RUSTIK's Living Lab operational phase began in May 2023 and ran through to late 2025. This section examines how RUSTIK Living Labs were put into practice across the 14 Pilot Regions. Whereas previous sections have explored the methodological design, here the focus shifts to how Living Labs were implemented in practice, the transition challenges they addressed, and the data experiments they designed and delivered. As the aim of this deliverable is to assess the implementation of the Living Labs methodology, the discussion draws primarily on Cycles 1 and 2, as documented in RUSTIK Deliverables 3.1 and 3.2. A closer focus on the results of each Living Lab, and on the outputs from Cycle 3, will follow in the forthcoming Deliverables 5.1 and 5.2.

Moving from how Living Labs approached participation and experimentation, the latter part of the section proposes a typology that captures the main implementation modes evident in RUSTIK. The section concludes by reflecting on the extent to which a Living Lab approach – as it was conceptualised in RUSTIK's methodological framework – was realised in practice.

4.1. Cycle 1

Cycle 1 ran from May to December 2023. As outlined in Section 3.3 above, it focused on planning possibilities for the Living Lab and culminated in the identification of a specific transition challenge for work to cohere around.

4.1.1. Activities undertaken during Cycle 1

Cycle 1 activities centred on establishing a shared understanding of each Pilot Region's context and transition priorities. Each Living Lab undertook a common set of analytical and participatory activities that provided a substantive basis for later cycles. These activities included:

- Contributing to WP1's compilation of geographic, demographic, and socio-economic regional profiles through stakeholder engagement and desk analysis.
- In parallel, contributing to WP2 by assessing data availability and quality as well as capacities for using data in the region, and identifying key gaps.
- Supporting institutional and policy mapping for WP4, by identifying actors, governance arrangements, and strategic frameworks shaping transition responses at regional and national levels.
- Within each Pilot Region, holding stakeholder workshops and bilateral meetings to explore local priorities and build participation.

Collectively, these activities helped clarify where Living Labs might add value within the Pilot Region, and improved understanding of relevant policy and data-related contexts. Stakeholder outreach surfaced common issues, such as uncertainty about available data, and the importance of grounding Living Lab work in existing strategies and capacities.

4.1.2. Transition challenges

Although all Pilot Regions began with RUSTIK's three focal transitions – socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital – most Living Labs refined their focus to one or two of these during Cycle 1. They then further narrowed the focus to a specific challenge (or opportunity) posed by that transition for the region.

While the approaches used to narrow focus varied, Living Labs consistently moved from broad transition categories to a clearly bounded challenge that was both regionally salient and actionable within the Living Lab methodology. In many cases, the selected transition challenge aligned with existing regional strategies or pressing governance concerns, which strengthened institutional engagement and provided a practical entry point for Living Lab work.

Four thematic groups by transition challenge emerged from Cycle 1. Table 8 summarises these alongside details of the selected transition challenge for each Living Lab and the data needs identified in *D2.2: Comparative Analysis of Living Lab Data Needs Investigations*.

Table 8: Comparison of Living Lab transition challenges and data needs

Living Lab	Focal transition	Transition challenge	Data needs
Thematic group 1: Entrepreneurship and local economic development			
Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT)	Socio-economic & demographic	Identifying needs of small rural businesses	Demographics, economic status, challenges faced by Small Rural Businesses, employment data
Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG)	Socio-economic & demographic	Strengthening the Rural Food System	Local population access, farming cooperation, vocational schools, visitor habits
Mazowieckie (PL)	Socio-economic & demographic	Transitioning economy	Detailed employment structures, local resources analysis, entrepreneurial sector insights
Świętokrzyskie (PL)	Socio-economic & demographic	Reversing demographic decline through rural tourism development	Insights on spatial distribution, tourist dynamics, rural area conditions
Zaječar (RS)	Socio-economic & demographic	Development of tourism and short food supply chains	Data on local food system participants, consumer preferences, tourism relevance
Thematic group 2: Land, planning, and natural resource management			
Garfagnana (IT)	Socio-economic & demographic + climate & environmental	Sustainable forestry for productive and environmental purposes + community projects	Social capital, quality of relationships, trust between people, reciprocity (qualitative)
Parma, Piacenza & Ferrara (IT)	Climate & environmental	Water availability and management for irrigation and production	Real-time data for water availability and demand
Galicia (ES)	Socio-economic & demographic + climate & environmental	Reconciling land use and ownership.	Land ownership, housing data, existing policy instruments
Thematic group 3: Young people and migration			
North Karelia (FI)	Socio-economic & demographic	Integration of immigrants	Population trends, immigrant background, job numbers, integration statuses

Living Lab	Focal transition	Transition challenge	Data needs
Monmouthshire (UK)	Socio-economic & demographic	Demographic change and youth retention	Reasons for youth migration, housing and educational/employment data, income limitations
Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)	Socio-economic & demographic	Making the region an attractive place to live and work for young people	Real-time data on people seeking jobs and apprenticeships, open positions. Qualitative surveying
Thematic group 4: Digital innovation and social inclusion			
Osona (ES) ¹	Socio-economic & demographic + climate & environmental	Improving quality of life via territorial and urban planning	Demographics, surveys, environmental, infrastructure data
Osrednjeslovenska (SI)	Socio-economic & demographic + climate & environmental	Excess food management and food access in rural areas	Real-time excess food data, social exclusion stats, subjective wellbeing metrics
Gloucestershire (UK)	Digital	Development of a resource and a strategy for enhanced digital inclusion	Assessing rural community digital access and confidence.

¹ Osona was initially clustered with Group 2, but the Living Lab team agreed that Group 4 was more resonant with their interests and ambitions.

4.2. Cycle 2

Cycle 2 ran throughout 2024, with some Living Labs continuing to finalise the Cycle in early 2025. As outlined in Sections 3.3 and 3.4 above, each Living Lab designed and delivered a data experiment during the cycle. The results and findings of these data experiments will be synthesised in Deliverable 5.1.

4.2.1. Activities undertaken during Cycle 2

Although the data experiments varied widely in scope and methodology, Living Labs undertook a broadly consistent set of activities to design and implement their experiments. These included:

- **Refining the data experiment focus** and clarifying the data and methods to be used, what was feasible within the timeframe, which stakeholders would need to be involved, and the expected practical value.
- **Collecting and preparing data** through both primary data collection and secondary data sourcing. In some cases, stakeholders were also engaged in data gathering.
- **Analysing** collected data using a range of methods and tools.
- **Engaging stakeholders** to test tools and approaches and to help interpret data and validate findings. This included convening cross-sector collaborations for consultation and to co-produce elements of the experiment.

- **Developing outputs** such as visualisations, maps, dashboards, integrated data sets, and policy briefs to provide evidence for decision-making.
- **Communication activities** tied to the experiment.
- Ongoing **coordination activities** between research and practice partners.

During this cycle, several Living Labs also began reflecting on how to apply results in Cycle 3 and on what might be needed to sustain or extend collaborations beyond the RUSTIK project.

4.2.2. Data experiment implementation

As the data experiments were collaboratively designed to meet the transition challenge identified for each Pilot Region, they varied widely in ambition and scope. However, implementation across the Living Labs reflected a shared commitment to testing new data, tools, or methods that could generate actionable insights. The experiments broadly fell into the following categories:

- Collecting new primary data where evidence gaps were acute.
- Integrating disparate datasets to produce new tools and improve understanding.
- Applying novel analytical techniques.
- Prototyping digital or participatory tools to support local learning and strategy development.

Table 9 summarises each Living Lab’s data experiment during Cycle 2, providing a comparative overview of how experimentation was operationalised.

Table 9: Data experiment comparison by Living Lab

Living Lab	Data experiment focus	Purpose	Core methods
Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT)	Mapping and profiling Small Rural Businesses	To improve visibility and understanding of SRBs	Data mapping, web scraping, survey, workshops
Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG)	Food system and inequality mapping	To understand local food networks and inclusion	Surveys, interviews, GIS, restaurant experiment
Rhein-Hunsrück (DE)	Youth ambitions and apprenticeship pathways	To address demographic decline	Youth/employer surveys, labour market analysis
Galicia (ES)	Land ownership and use decision-support tool	To address fragmentation challenges	Spatial modelling, multicriteria analysis, interviews
Osona (ES)	Quality of life mapping and cohesion analysis	To assess territorial disparities	Web scraping, fieldwork, participatory mapping
North Karelia (FI)	Immigrant integration and labour market pathways	To support demographic transition	Expert interviews, surveys, programme analysis
Garfagnana (IT)	Sustainable forest use and socio-environmental coherence	To integrate land management data	Workshops, data integration, spatial analysis

Living Lab	Data experiment focus	Purpose	Core methods
Parma–Piacenza–Ferrara (IT)	Water availability and irrigation dynamics	To anticipate climate impacts	Dataset creation, mapping, climatic analysis
Mazowieckie (PL)	Local resource potential and economic transition	To identify development pathways	Surveys, interviews, participatory workshops
Świętokrzyskie (PL)	Rural tourism mapping	To support tourism-led demographic renewal	Data inventory, surveys
Zaječar (RS)	Tourism and short supply chain networks	To understand socio-economic relations	Surveys, focus groups, social network analysis
Osrednjeslovenska (SI)	Food redistribution modelling	To analyse food loss and social inclusion	Data processing, modelling
Gloucestershire (UK)	Digital inclusion dashboard tool	To improve access to data and strategy design	Interviews, stakeholder engagement, prototyping
Monmouthshire (UK)	Youth retention and future prospects dashboard	To support demographic strategy	Participatory mapping, interviews.

The variation in the focus of Living Labs’ data experiments, in addition to the varying purposes and methods used, led to diversity in Living Labs’ experiences of the process. The differences in experience, including the opportunities and challenges presented through the Living Lab approach, were explored through twenty-seven semi-structured interviews with Living Lab Coordinators and Pilot Region Partners in September and October 2025. Section 5 presents the key findings from these interviews alongside additional insights from the Living Labs’ Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 reports.

5. Insights and reflections on implementation

This section examines how RUSTIK's Living Lab methodology functioned in practice, drawing on learning and reflections documented in the Living Lab reports for Cycles 1 and 2, alongside qualitative insights from interviews with Living Lab Coordinators and Pilot Region Partners during Cycle 3. The section focuses on partners' experiences of implementation, including how the methodology was understood and applied, how collaborative activities occurred, and how experimentation worked in practice. The section provides a grounded account of the barriers and enablers that Living Labs encountered and highlights the practical conditions that influenced participation, co-design, data work, and pathways to impact. These insights help explain variation across the Living Labs and offer lessons for future practice.

5.1. Insights from implementation

This subsection describes insights emerging from Cycle 1, during which Living Labs identified their transition challenge, and Cycle 2, during which Living Labs designed and delivered their data experiments. It synthesises the learning that Living Labs reported in D3.1 and D3.2.

5.1.1. Lessons from Cycle 1

Insights from implementation in Cycle 1, taken from the Living Labs' reports that comprise D3.1, point to factors that influenced how Living Labs activities were subsequently delivered. In practice, Cycle 1 **functioned as a period of diagnostic and relational work**, during which Living Labs explored initial assumptions about institutional capacity, stakeholder engagement, policy relevance, and data availability. In several cases, this led Living Labs to recalibrate both their methods and expectations.

Stakeholder readiness and institutional capacity were key enabling factors; however, the fourteen Living Labs started from different points in this regard. Some began Cycle 1 with well-developed partnerships and prior experience of collaboration. In Galicia (ES), for example, previous cooperation between the academic team and the Pilot Region Partner enabled relatively smooth early coordination. In Rhein-Hunsrück (DE), existing participatory approaches associated with an active LEADER group provided a good foundation for engagement. Other Living Labs necessarily used Cycle 1 as a more explicit capacity and relationship-building phase. For example, the Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG) Living Lab invested early effort in clarifying responsibilities between the core partners and establishing relationships with a wider deliberative circle. In this example, **clearly defining roles early in the process set the groundwork for later collaboration**.

Across the Living Labs, involving a **diverse range of stakeholders** in early engagement activities was generally seen as beneficial, since this supported mutual learning and broadened perspectives on regional transition challenges. However, diversity alone was not sufficient to ensure meaningful engagement. Several Living Labs found that levels of stakeholder interest and participation were uneven, with some stakeholders highly proactive and others harder to engage. For example, Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT) benefited from some well-networked stakeholders who were active in regional development but had more difficulty reaching previously unengaged stakeholders. Some Living Labs also initially struggled to communicate their purpose and value, especially to stakeholders who had limited familiarity with participatory or data-driven approaches.

University-based researchers in Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG) were outsiders to the region, and stakeholders were initially uncertain about how Living Lab activities could provide practical benefits. Communicating the added value required time and repeated engagement. Where the Pilot Region Partner had **strong pre-existing networks**, these often proved crucial in encouraging wider involvement.

In some cases, difficulties emerged between practice-oriented and research-oriented partners or stakeholders. These were often linked to **differences in expectations or working cultures**, or differing perspectives on whether practical or analytical activities were more relevant for the Living Lab. Forms of **translation and mediation** were therefore important for building effective relationships. For example, Rhein-Hunsrück (DE) found that time and effort were needed to find a common ‘language’ for discussing complex transition challenges among stakeholders. Despite these early difficulties, most Living Labs recognised that bringing together different perspectives enriched the process.

Although all Living Labs began Cycle 1 working across RUSTIK’s three key transitions, finding a more meaningful and actionable local focus was integral to Cycle 1. Many Living Labs found that **narrowing focus was more difficult and time-consuming than anticipated**. In some cases, prior initiatives in the region complicated decisions about where the Living Lab could add distinct value. Others found that the breadth of issues explored made prioritisation challenging. For example, discussions in North Karelia (FI) covered all three transitions and focusing in on a specific challenge came relatively late in Cycle 1. Similarly, in Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara (IT), climate change was an obvious shared concern, but the implications of demographic and digital transitions were less clear and required further exploration.

Several Living Labs used Cycle 1 to **actively reduce their scope** in order to remain realistic and policy relevant. Both Osona (ES) and Mazowieckie (PL) reduced their geographical scope. In Osona’s case, this was to align with the Pilot Region Partner’s remit and influence. For Mazowieckie, working at the level of a large voivodeship (region) was not practically feasible, and focusing on a specific district offered more practical opportunities. In other cases, reducing scope meant finding a more concrete and actionable entry point. In Rhein-Hunsrück, initial discussions centred on the broad ambition of making the region attractive for young people. Stakeholder engagement relevant literature gradually redirected attention towards the more specific challenge of labour shortages and unfilled apprenticeships.

Relatedly, **sequencing** also played an important role in Cycle 1. Many Living Labs found that analytical tasks for the project such as institutional mapping felt abstract or disconnected until a concrete transition challenge had been identified, after which such tasks became substantially more meaningful. This suggests that, in practice, Cycle 1 operated less as a linear sequence of tasks and more as an iterative sense-making process, in which the value of different activities often became apparent retrospectively.

Living Labs undertook preliminary **data scoping** during Cycle 1, and this proved an area where both significant differences and valuable learning emerged. Several Living Labs had initially approached data issues through the lens of absent datasets. However, Cycle 1 activities surfaced more fundamental issues related to fragmented data, limited spatial granularity, restricted access, or weak capacity to interpret data. In North Karelia (FI), for example, the Living Lab benefited from good access to national and regional statistical data and from internal

organisational capacity for data analysis. However, focus group discussions revealed that the principal issues lay in dispersed data and a lack of evidence on specific issues such as regional attractiveness, motivations for migration, and wellbeing. Similarly, Zaječar (RS) found that narrowing the transition challenge revealed key gaps in data around primary food system actors and local market capacities. In Rhein-Hunsrück (DE), while relevant socio-economic and demographic data existed, this was often only available at NUTS3 or higher levels and scattered across institutions. For some Living Labs, data issues had more immediate consequences for progress. Osona (ES) began with a clear conceptual focus but struggled to access the data needed to substantiate this. Garfagnana (IT) found that insufficient data on the forestry sector limited assessments of multifunctionality. These experiences demonstrate that identifying data gaps was not simply a technical exercise but a critical step in determining what kinds of data experiments would be feasible in each context.

Finally, Cycle 1 highlighted the extent to which Living Lab processes could be influenced by **external contextual constraints**. Political volatility, staff changes, competing organisational priorities, and time pressures were all cited as constraining factors. These constraints were not exceptional but reflected the embedded nature of Living Labs. Recognising and working with these conditions emerged as a key part of Cycle 1 learning, reinforcing the importance of being realistic and adaptable in later cycles.

Overall, Cycle 1 differentiated Living Lab trajectories by surfacing variation in institutional capacity, stakeholder dynamics, feasible ambition, and data accessibility. These conditions had knock-on effects for how each Living Lab approached the data experiments in Cycle 2.

5.1.2. Lessons from Cycle 2

During Cycle 2, data experiments reflected not only the potential of new data, tools, and methods for addressing transition challenges but also the conditions under which these can be most effective. In general, Cycle 2 demonstrated that data experimentation in rural Living Labs is less about technical innovation *per se* and more about **building the conditions under which relevant data can be used**.

As already noted for Cycle 1 above, the **practical realities of working with data in and about rural areas** raised challenges. The Living Lab reports that Living Lab Coordinators and Pilot Region Partners completed for Cycle 2 (presented in D3.2) highlighted issues such as limited granularity, inconsistent classifications, and missing or outdated records, which required substantial effort to source, clean, validate, and link data. For example, Living Labs working on land, planning, and natural resource management found that core datasets were often poorly aligned. In Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara (IT), water governance data relevant to agricultural irrigation and climate adaptation were dispersed across multiple bodies and used different formats. Similarly, in Galicia (ES), inconsistencies in cadastral and settlement data required harmonisation before a usable decision support system could be developed.

A few Living Labs encountered issues around **data governance and ethical or regulatory compliance**, which led to unanticipated delays or redesigns. Researchers in Monmouthshire (UK) required formal criminal record checks to work with young people in schools. Osrednjeslovenska (SI) needed to contend with revised institutional rules on research with people, which required a retroactive ethical review. While these issues temporarily constrained data collection, they also

added legitimacy and assurance to the Living Labs. Elsewhere, governance constraints affected how data could be operationalised rather than whether it could be collected. In Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT), for example, GDPR considerations limited the extent to which a shared regional data pool could be developed, despite strong political buy-in and clear strategic value.

Some Living Labs shifted emphasis towards **building reliable baseline datasets**, especially where existing data was either too coarse or poorly suited to local action. For instance, Świętokrzyskie (PL) observed that abundant national data on demographics and tourism were not sufficiently tailored to the needs of local actors, prompting new primary data collection through surveys and stakeholder workshops. For Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT), initial plans to use web scraping to map small rural businesses needed to be supplemented with in situ data gathering because many businesses did not have a sufficient digital footprint. As these examples suggest, the importance of **improving data fitness for purpose** emerged as a key lesson during Cycle 2.

In this regard, **matching experimental ambition to available capacities** (such as time, skills, and institutional support) was a vital enabling factor. The Living Labs that designed data experiments which were closely aligned with their capabilities were generally better able to develop usable outputs within the Cycle 2 timeframe. Data experiments that relied on extensive new data collection or complex modelling were more likely to encounter bottlenecks. In some cases, Living Labs needed to reduce their scope or adjust their methods. While these adaptations were often productive, they emphasise that innovation in Living Labs is context-dependent and what counts as 'new' does not necessarily mean technical novelty. Nockregion-Oberkärnten's (AT) relatively simple infographic and spatial business map proved compelling for engaging mayors and informing regional strategy discussions. In Mazowieckie (PL), structured surveys and workshops around a local natural resource generated actionable insights for entrepreneurship without relying on advanced analytics. These examples demonstrate that **feasible, well-targeted experiments** – rather than overly ambitious designs – are more likely to support learning and decision-making in rural contexts.

As this suggests, **stakeholder participation** continued to be crucial during this cycle. For some Living Labs, experimentation provided a means to include those who might otherwise not have been engaged in more policy-focused activities. For example, Osona (ES) introduced participatory mapping and photo elicitation activities, which allowed residents to participate in new ways. Monmouthshire (UK) also used participatory mapping and conducted regular community outreach activities to engage with younger residents. These examples show how data experiments could themselves catalyse collaboration, even where their immediate analytical outputs were modest.

Similarly, activities around assembling data, defining indicators, and creating maps frequently brought together stakeholders who had not previously worked together. For example, in Zaječar (RS) and Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara (IT), efforts to map food supply chains and irrigation systems, respectively, **prompted new conversations** between farmers, businesses, public authorities, and intermediaries. In some cases, these interactions were valued as much as the data outputs themselves, as they helped articulate shared challenges and identify areas for coordinated action.

At the same time, several Living Labs found that maintaining engagement required sustained effort and adaptation as their work evolved. Where this was successful, **participatory processes** could both ground analysis in local experience and build confidence among stakeholders in using and interpreting data. However, a few Living Labs experienced difficulties sustaining engagement

with stakeholders when activities paused, underlining the need for regular communication and facilitation.

Cycle 2 also continued to contribute to **relationship-building** between partners. Both clear task allocation and regular communication were underscored as crucial to successful collaboration between Pilot Region Partners and Living Lab Coordinators. Where these support factors were present and effective, relationships were strengthened, and by the end of Cycle 2, several partners had already expressed their intentions to continue collaborating beyond RUSTIK. By contrast, one team identified in hindsight that investing more time in developing the relationship between the Pilot Region Partner and Living Lab Coordinator before launching the data experiment would have improved implementation.

Cycle 2 further contributed to **skill development** across teams. Partners reported learning new skills in technical areas, such as GIS, survey design, and data integration. Softer skills, particularly around participatory methods and stakeholder engagement, were also commonly reported.

5.2. Interview reflections

Towards the end of Cycle 3 (September and October 2025), twenty-seven semi-structured interviews were conducted with Living Lab Coordinators and Pilot Region Partners from each Living Lab. Most interviews were conducted separately with Living Lab Coordinators and Pilot Region Partners to provide space for more individual reflections, although three were joint interviews involving both partners. Interviews were conducted by a neutral researcher previously unaffiliated with the project. The interviews sought to **gather in-depth reflections** on the practical implementation of the Living Lab approach across diverse regional contexts. Questions covered reflections on how the methodology was operationalised, the hurdles and benefits encountered, and the added value and impact of the Living Lab approach on project outcomes. The interview guide is provided in Appendix A.

The interviews provided anonymity to participants so that they could speak freely about their experiences. In accordance with this, the following summary of findings does not name specific Living Labs. Anonymised quotes are included to provide illustrative examples of key points.

5.2.1. Experiences and understanding of the Living Lab approach

Participants had varied experience with Living Labs. Only four had previously worked directly within Living Labs, while ten had taken part in similar participatory or collaborative approaches. The remaining twelve said this was their first time working on a project of this kind. Most of those with prior experience were academic partners.

Participants described mixed initial impressions of Living Labs at the start of RUSTIK. Fifteen said they felt **uncertain about what the methodology would involve**, how Living Labs would be organised, and what their role would be. Five were unsure about how the approach would differ from other participatory methodologies they had used before. Work Package Leads were seen as important in helping to clarify the approach, with partners appreciating online meetings to clarify expectations. However, the **importance of having clear guidance** was underscored, and two participants noted that it had been helpful to work in a team where someone already had Living Lab experience. For example, one stated:

“I had a lot of support from colleagues (...) who’ve had a lot of experience with working with Living Labs, which was really important. And I did then feel informed going into the process”.

By the end of Cycle 3, participants’ understanding of Living Labs had become more concrete. When asked how they now understood the methodology, common themes included:

- Extensive collaboration with stakeholders,
- Co-producing meaningful outcomes rather than simply producing outputs,
- Close co-operation between academic and practice partners,
- Place-based work,
- Iterative and flexible processes.

These ideas are reflected in participants’ own words:

“I guess maybe a good analogy would be that you’re taking the research out of the Petri dish (...) it becomes more hands-on, more practical, hopefully more grounded in reality”.

“Doing a Living Lab is an equal collaboration between various partners from different backgrounds. For me, it is the scientific partner working with the regional partner and the stakeholders, and the aim of the Living Lab is to develop something jointly”.

“It is a process of open, iterative, transparent collaboration towards a shared goal”.

Alongside these positive reflections, respondents also identified difficulties. In both interviews and the Living Lab reports, some teams noted that the approach is **time-consuming**. Other difficulties raised included:

- Pressure to be innovative,
- Blurred responsibilities,
- Unpredictable outcomes,
- Managing conflicting stakeholder views.

These concerns are also captured in the following participant quotes:

“It was a bit left, right, back and forth. It was (...) not super straightforward. I think it was very time-consuming”.

“Sometimes I thought, now we have to do it in this way, and we have to have an innovative data experiment. That’s not so easy if you have these empirical data asks from [stakeholders]”.

Despite these difficulties, most participants remained positive about the approach. However, two academic partners questioned whether the RUSTIK Living Labs substantively differed from other place-based and participatory approaches, and one viewed the term as a buzzword rather than a distinct methodology.

5.2.2. Methodological functionality

Participants were invited to reflect on the suitability of the Living Lab approach within their Pilot Region. Most regarded the Living Lab approach as broadly appropriate and successful in their

context. Relevant local benefits reported included:

- Deepening understanding of regional dynamics,
- Encouraging partners and stakeholders to adopt new perspectives on key challenges for the region,
- Facilitating engagement with stakeholders who might not have been involved in more conventional approaches,
- Bringing together previously disconnected stakeholders within the region,
- Fostering longer-term collaboration that may lead to future joint initiatives,
- Creating a sense of local ownership unlikely to emerge through other approaches.

However, different opinions also emerged. Five participants valued the opportunity to work at a regional scale, particularly practice partners who noted a frequent lack of data focus at this level. For example, one participant explained:

“It was a good possibility for us to have scientists in our team and to have them look at our region and find out more about our region (...) We don’t have the data as a background for these projects, so it was really good to get the data and a scientific background”.

Conversely, three participants felt that a smaller scale might have been more effective, as the broader scope sometimes introduced complexity and coordination challenges. As one reflected:

“Our Living Lab was connected with the region, which is a very large area (...), and at the regional scale, Living Labs tend to lack strong practical support”.

Two academic partners voiced stronger criticism, viewing the Living Lab methodology as somewhat forced in their context and questioning its suitability. These concerns are captured in the following quotes:

“I don’t think the Living Lab worked as well as we’d hoped in [region], and I don’t think what we did was a Living Lab”.

“I’m not such a fan of this methodology. Living Labs, it’s just a name. It’s just the new fashion to name everything as modern”.

In general, participants who had **active existing regional initiatives and strong institutional structures** found the Living Lab approach easier to implement and more beneficial. Similarly, partners who from the outset proactively **aligned the Living Lab with relevant policy objectives**, such as regional development strategies, reported greater utility and impact.

Partners were also asked to specifically reflect on the Living Lab methodology’s suitability for addressing the transition challenge identified in their regions. Several interviewees, particularly practice partners for whom the transition challenge was an area of focus in their work outside of RUSTIK, viewed the approach as particularly valuable in this regard. The benefits noted included:

- Broadening the scope of stakeholder engagement and involving diverse stakeholders who had previously been overlooked in policy discussions.
- Facilitating connections between stakeholders at different levels, fostering new cross-scale collaborations.

- Providing important learning opportunities for stakeholders in particular sectors or areas.

Three academic partners considered that the Living Lab approach was not *especially* useful to their challenge; because the approach is highly adaptable, they viewed it as so flexible that it was potentially applicable in any context. For example, one participant noted:

“It’s hard to say if it was especially good for our theme (...) For me, it’s more about the trial-and-error approach, and I think it would have worked well with all the themes”.

Notably, there were **mixed views on the value of the preparation and envisioning activities** in Cycle 1. Six participants highlighted the value in deliberating over the transition challenge and uncovering key issues that might otherwise have been overlooked. As one reported:

“We would not have addressed the topic itself if it weren’t for the Living Lab approach because the topic came from the stakeholders in the regions (...) I like the cycles. I like the thinking and these cycles a lot. First, to define your question, define your challenge, then define and work on your data experiment”.

However, three considered that these activities took time that could have been used for implementing research or engaging with policymakers. These concerns are exemplified by the following participant feedback:

“The broad challenges during the first year, there were a lot of tasks given (...) we needed to work on this for a long time, and it was a lot of work”.

“The iterative process of developing and implementing the project took so much time (...) So in terms of efficiency, I would doubt if it was efficient”.

More broadly, a few participants felt that the diversity of the transition challenges that emerged from Cycle 1 was itself challenging; partners from two Living Labs considered that their focus significantly diverged from others, limiting their opportunities for peer learning.

5.2.3. Co-design and collaboration dynamics

Each participant was asked to reflect on their relationship with their partner organisation (academic or practice) in their Living Lab. Most described the **co-leadership relationship as generally positive**, even if there had been a few minor problems. Eight participants were extremely positive about their counterpart and did not identify any issues. Amongst others, common issues reported concerned **navigating individual relationships** and **maintaining regular communication**.

Seven participants experienced tensions arising from **differences in approach**, with the Pilot Region Partner being more practice-oriented and the Living Lab Coordinator more academically focused. However, most of these found that, over time, they were able to find a compromise and develop a shared, positive way forward. Five reflected that they had ultimately learned a lot from their counterpart, with practice partners valuing gaining new knowledge from academic partners, and academic partners highlighting the value of gaining practical experience from practice partners. These learning processes are illustrated in the following:

“We both learned from the other (...) the research approach that [the academic partner] had is not always based on the practical situation because it’s more academic, and what we had is insights from the field that maybe helped the whole process be more based on reality”.

“Sometimes [the academic partner] say this and this, and this approach is scientific, and so on. And then I go home and read (...) so it was like learning by doing”.

“We learned a lot from [the practice partner] and the technicians implementing the [data experiment]”.

Two Living Labs experienced issues arising from, respectively, the practice partner’s lack of capacity to engage fully and their vested interest as a regional stakeholder. This had sometimes affected how other regional stakeholders perceived the Living Lab. Additionally, two Living Labs that had secondment structures within their partnerships, in which a researcher was seconded to the practice partner organisation, felt that these had not been effective; secondees did not feel fully embedded in their host team and sometimes felt isolated.

Challenges also arose around **uneven responsibilities**, although experiences were mixed. Some academic partners felt that their practice partner counterpart had been insufficiently engaged in RUSTIK. Furthermore, four participants felt that their counterpart had placed too much responsibility upon them – for example, for stakeholder engagement, data collection, or report writing. Notably, partners that did not report this issue often cited **clearly defined responsibilities** as a key strength of their Living Labs in both the interviews and Living Lab reports. They achieved this through **regular meetings, shared project tools, and clear planning from the outset**. For example, one participant reflected:

“It has been really easy (...) we established that once a week we will meet for at least 15 minutes (...) then we had a sort of Trello dashboard where we put everything, the deadlines, the milestones, so if something was [the practice partner’s] responsibility, they would put it in. So everything was really clear”.

Having a **pre-existing relationship** between the partner organisations also emerged as a major advantage, as it reduced the time needed to build trust and establish working relationships. This is reflected in the following quote from one partner:

“The cooperation within this project was almost without any significant issues (...) It has to be noted that [the practice partner] and [the academic partner] already have an established long-term cooperation from the past, so that’s why”.

Three partners also noted that the Living Lab methodology took a more integrated approach to collaboration than they had previously experienced. Practice partners appreciated being more involved in project design and having greater control over aspects such as budgeting.

5.2.4. Operational challenges and constraints

Many of the operational challenges partners mentioned involved stakeholder engagement. Most described difficulties in **engaging stakeholders and maintaining their interest** and involvement throughout the project. Issues cited across interviews and reports included:

- Time and funding constraints limiting stakeholder participation.
- Time required to build trust with stakeholders.
- Sustaining stakeholder interest over time.
- Explaining the concept of Living Labs to stakeholders, particularly local residents.

- Conveying the value of participation and communicating what stakeholders would gain from being involved.
- Some stakeholders approaching the process competitively rather than collaboratively.

Participants captured some of these issues in their own words:

“The issues were mostly related to the involvement of the [stakeholders]. It was very challenging (...) Also, along the process, the engagement weakened (...) It was hard to keep them interested”.

“It was quite difficult to explain to stakeholders or people who work here in [region], what exactly is a living lab? What are we doing?”.

“Stakeholder engagement does come up as a challenge. We did go to many events, and the response rates increased after each event (...) but again it is a time thing”.

“It was difficult to gather people (...) and show them something has happened (...) I wish we could give them something to participate in this process because I know at the end something has happened, but these people, they don’t feel it”.

Often, the **pre-existing regional networks** maintained by practice partners proved critical to successful stakeholder involvement, as exemplified in the quotes below:

“[The practice partner] are much closer to the community (...) so the initial phase or cycle before we entered into the actual experiment (...) that needed a lot of networking activities and collaboration with stakeholders (...) that would not have been possible without their collaboration”.

“[The practice partner] has a very wide network, and we are quite well known as respected. So it was quite easy to invite and get people from different sectors to, you know, get interested and to join these meetings”.

The flexible nature of the Living Lab approach was viewed as beneficial but also presented operational challenges. As noted above, several Living Labs found the development process **time- and resource-intensive**. Engaging stakeholders in defining the Living Lab’s focus could prove difficult, with some participants identifying that stakeholders had, in particular, **lacked the knowledge needed** to identify relevant gaps for the data experiment. For example, one reported:

“I think local stakeholders were forced to identify the problem because you are asking them what are their needs for data (...) They are saying, no, we don’t have a problem (...) They are not aware of where the gaps are in their knowledge, in their capacities and understanding”.

Political dynamics within the Pilot Regions further influenced Living Labs’ success. For some, changes in local or regional government had adversely impacted the relevance of Living Lab activities. For others, fluctuations in national government interest had constrained opportunities for policy engagement.

More prosaic operational challenges emerged for partners themselves. These included:

- Staff changes in partner organisations, which caused delays or disrupted established

working relationships.

- Partners who were geographically dispersed, requiring travel.
- Difficulties coordinating schedules.
- Insufficient digital skills to engage with some tasks.

As participants reflected:

“We had a very good project manager (...) but she was on maternity for quite a long time (...) We were very happy for her, but it caused some problems for our project”.

“Another challenge for us was the issue of location (...) [the pilot region] was a commute of at least five to six hours by train (...) We tried to be there quite often (...) so it was very time-consuming, all the commuting”.

5.2.5. Outcomes, added value, and impact pathways

Fourteen participants considered that their Living Lab had created **deeper collaboration between academic and practice partners** than would have been anticipated in a more conventional research project. Pilot Region Partners particularly reported feeling **greater ownership** and taking a more active role in research design and data collection. Both partner types reported that they had benefited from **accessing each other’s networks** and had expanded their own through the collaboration. For example, one interviewee stated:

“We have new practical things like relationships (...) with [the practice partner] and with other organisations that are working in [the pilot region]”.

Participants further highlighted that work in the Living Lab was more hands-on and oriented towards real-world applications, with increased stakeholder engagement. Other differences from previous projects noted included:

- More scope for testing ideas and learning from failure.
- Greater flexibility in timescales, focus, and structure.
- Encouragement of innovative methods.

Examples of these perceptions are shown in the following quotes:

“[A lab] is a safe space to experiment, so therefore you don’t have to worry when stuff blows up (...) you just wipe it down and try another chemical. And in a way, that’s what we’re doing with social innovation”.

“The process is iterative, and you have to test it and see how it goes. Share the results, start the process again”.

“I really like this trial-and-error approach. I like that you have the chance to test and then go back and so on”.

Five participants were unsure about whether the differences they perceived in their work within RUSTIK were directly due to the Living Lab methodology or caused by other factors. For example, one stated:

“This steady collaboration between two partners (...) I’ve never experienced that in any approach or framework (...) But I’m not sure how to evaluate whether this should be treated as something as RUSTIK contributed or the Living Lab approach”.

One participant did not believe that they had done anything notably different from other projects. Furthermore, two actually felt that the methodological requirements of the data experiment had constrained their approach. For example, one interviewee reported:

“We sometimes felt like the data experiment felt kind of like a corset or something that we had strict requirements that our work had to fit into (...) We had to make sure it was somehow innovative and fit the requirements”.

When asked about the **short-term outcomes** of the Living Lab, most partners emphasised the results of their data experiment, including models, tools, and survey instruments that they had developed. Other outcomes noted included:

- Gaining new knowledge about a topic, sector, method, or digital technology.
- Developing new relationships, including with the other partner, stakeholders, and other RUSTIK Living Labs.
- New or re-established networks between stakeholders in the Pilot Region.

These outcomes were seen as being supported by the Living Lab’s **emphasis on stakeholder engagement and by regular knowledge exchange** through project meetings and other fora. Further, participants generally perceived that the Living Lab approach had **increased the social acceptance** of their results. For example, one reported:

“Acceptance in the society or in the region is probably much higher for the entire project, the methods and the outcomes [because] it doesn’t have this top-down approach”.

Participants were also asked about how their Living Lab work had been – or was being – translated into **concrete interventions or policy recommendations**. Nine reported that their outputs were expected to be used or incorporated into initiatives such as regional strategies or development plans. Four noted that the models, tools, or results they had generated were already being used by intended stakeholders to support specific objectives. For two others, findings had already influenced a particular policy related to their transition challenge, and a further two anticipated that their findings would contribute to shaping a wider national policy. Other reported outcomes included informing guidance documents and supporting future funding applications.

However, some noted that, as their work was still ongoing, it was too early to identify specific outcomes; this reflects that the conclusion of the Living Lab operational cycles does not mean the end of learning and contributing to change for the Living Labs. As explained in Section 1.1.1, it is expected that synthesis and communications will continue in the final project year, and these operational phases provide Living Labs with an opportunity to build the foundations for continued collaboration. For example, some participants explained that relevant policymakers had expressed interest in their work but that tangible actions had not yet emerged. These sentiments are reflected in the following quotes:

“The whole policy implementation phase, I think this might take a little bit more time, and yeah, we are still working on this”.

“[Policy body] has already said that if we get some interesting results out, they will try and take this example to the ministry level and try to lobby (...) Of course, I don’t know if this will even happen. We don’t even have the results of the data experiment yet”.

“We need the time when the RUSTIK project ends to share all of the knowledge inside [the practice partner] (...) What we expect at this time is quite difficult to say”.

Many partners described **policy translation as one of the more challenging aspects** of the Living Lab methodology. Common difficulties included:

- Limited access to key policy decision-makers.
- Low external awareness of results.
- Concerns around data sharing and confidentiality.
- Initial confusion from policy stakeholders about the Living Lab approach.

For example, participants stated:

“It’s always the situation when you have new data on the table and the new methodology for collecting the data, and you put it on the table and when people look at it, they say, ok, is it really so? (...) So, first scepticism, and after explaining the methodology and the ways we obtained the result led to a change in their minds and perspective”.

“The policy issues, those are big ones that [the practice partner] doesn’t always have control over, and even those they do have control over, they’re very constrained in terms of what they can do by the resources they have available”.

Despite these challenges, some participants considered that the Living Lab approach had encouraged **greater communication with policy stakeholders throughout the project** and made the resulting data more understandable and relevant. Partner roles were also frequently noted in this respect, with the Pilot Region Partner seen as increasing access to policymakers and the academic partners seen as enhancing the credibility of results.

Participants also reflected on how they anticipated the data generated being used beyond RUSTIK. Many noted that data from their Living Lab would continue to be accessible through the **RUSTIK data viewer** and could be useful for researchers and policymakers in future. Four explained that the methods, tools, or surveys they had developed could be repeated or updated in the future. Another four noted that the tool or model they had developed was potentially scalable or replicable in other contexts. However, **future data use** was also seen as a key challenge. Reported barriers included:

- Limited time and capacity.
- The risk of data becoming quickly outdated.
- Staff turnover affecting use or transfer of results.
- Specific or localised data limiting use or replication.
- Changing political contexts affecting future priorities.

Participants reflected on these barriers:

“You have to collect data in the field. You have to do different surveys of the population, and this is time, this is work, this is money. This is all the things we don’t have. This is a problem, a great problem”.

“It depends on what manner [the data] are kept up to date. Because while historical datasets can be handy occasionally, for most organisations, up-to-date data or means of being able to collect them is often more important”.

“[The data is] very specific; it couldn’t be applied to other contexts because it’s very topic specific”.

5.2.6. Reflections on Living Labs in practice

Participants were asked to reflect on what they would change if they were to set up their Living Lab again. A few would not make changes, but most **identified aspects that they would change**, including:

- Selecting a different partner to collaborate with.
- Skipping or reducing the time-consuming investigation of multiple topics during the early stages of the Living Lab.
- Setting clearer goals around intended outcomes or policy influence from the outset.
- Adjusting approaches to stakeholder engagement, either by increasing engagement or managing expectations more effectively.
- Having more opportunities to engage with other Living Labs.

Some of these reflections are exemplified below:

“I would make the scope more narrow from the beginning, so instead of giving these three transitions (...) I don’t care if it’s digital, or environment or social demographic, but just choose one”.

“Perhaps we would be a bit more cautious with expectations, knowing that, in the end, for the policy partner, priorities may change”.

“If we had the opportunity to start again, we would spend more time trying to create synergies between stakeholders”.

“It would have been very useful for us to compare experiences with other Living Labs”.

Participants were also asked whether they would use the Living Lab approach again, specifically in **future rural development projects**. All partners expressed a willingness to do so, and most agreed that it was a valuable approach. However, several caveats were raised, especially by practice partners. There were some concerns about the potential challenges of implementing the Living Lab methodology outside of an EU-funded project. Partners also cautioned that the suitability of the approach would depend on the specific topic or context.

Furthermore, three academic partners remained unconvinced about the added value of the Living

Lab approach compared to other place-based or participatory approaches, and one partner suggested that the full approach may not always be necessary, with project teams instead selecting the most useful components.

5.3. Overarching insights

Across the three cycles, RUSTIK's Living Lab approach functioned less as a standardised methodology and more as an adaptive framework shaped by contexts, capacities, and dynamics in the Pilot Regions. Cycle 1 operated primarily as a **diagnostic and relational** phase, revealing local realities and data readiness. The groundwork laid and decisions made here strongly influenced later activities, and this was the phase that partners were most likely to revisit in hindsight. Cycle 2 demonstrated that data experimentation in rural contexts does not necessarily require technical novelty, but rests on **aligning data work with local needs and available skills and time**. Living Labs found that they generated value not only through analytical inputs but through jointly making sense of results and building relationships, often blurring the boundary between process and outcome.

These insights suggest that Living Labs are most effective when expectations are realistic, roles are clear, and flexibility is treated as a strength rather than a weakness. Across the operational period, co-design processes, stakeholder engagement activities, and data work were mutually reinforcing, but also fragile, requiring sustained facilitation and ongoing adaptation to both organisational capacities and external factors. Importantly, what counted as success varied across contexts. Modest, well-targeted experiments could prove more impactful than ambitious technical designs. The following synthesis section builds on these insights from implementation.

6. Synthesis: Lessons learned

This section brings together the evidence and reflections presented in the preceding sections to identify what has been learned from implementing Living Labs in RUSTIK's fourteen Pilot Regions. It provides a synthesis of how Living Labs operated in practice, the conditions that shaped their implementation, and the lessons that emerge. Based on these observations, the section presents a fourfold typology of RUSTIK Living Labs by implementation plus develops a programme level Theory of Change to articulate the relationships between activities, assumptions, and intended outcomes. In doing so, it highlights implications for place-based innovation processes and reflects on both the value and limitations of the Living Lab methodology.

6.1. Lessons from implementation

The implementation of the Living Lab approach across RUSTIK's 14 Pilot Regions reveals considerable diversity in how collaboration and experimentation unfolded in practice. Although all Living Labs began with the same methodological framework, the ways in which partners operationalised their approach differed substantially. This diversity was expected, as it is well-recognised in the literature and due to the nature of the methodology.

Cycle 1 revealed **contextual differences in readiness and capacity** that had a strong influence on the trajectory of Living Lab activities. Pilot Regions varied in the extent to which there were relevant existing partnerships and the strength and capacity of their governance arrangements. In Pilot Regions with **high institutional capacity, stable governance, and established coordination mechanisms**, Living Labs were able to progress quickly into focused activities and towards more ambitious data experiment designs.

Regions where relationships were weaker or **institutional capacity was limited or unstable faced constraints to implementation**. Their early work often needed to centre on building trust and finding a manageable shared focus. As Living Labs progressed, organisational changes, lack of staff time, limited administrative systems, and more fragmented governance arrangements resulted in more **unanticipated contingencies**. Living Labs that faced these difficulties sometimes needed to scale back their plans or turn to alternative methods in response.

Parallels emerge in how Living Labs were able to implement **iteration and feedback loops**. While some Living Labs successfully integrated forms of reflection and adaptation into their activities, others experienced issues such as practical delays, staffing changes, or shifting institutional priorities that limited their ability to do so. Where iterative processes functioned well, they helped refine the work and strengthen its relevance. Where constraints emerged, Living Labs tended to adopt more linear modes of implementation and were less able to engage in iterative 'learning by doing'.

Narrowing RUSTIK's three broad transition themes – socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital – into more **focused and actionable regional challenges** also proved key to effective implementation. Narrowing focus allowed Living Lab partners to converge on issues aligned with key priorities or strategic agendas for the region. Having a **clearly defined and locally compelling transition challenge** for the Living Lab to cohere around strengthened

engagement and helped ensure that activities were relevant to stakeholders. This was a vital part of embedding Living Labs in their regions, but it also set Living Labs on diverse pathways that, in some cases, reduced opportunities for sharing learning *between* regions. Moreover, since decisions about focus also determined the scope of experimentation, early issues or imbalances could create later constraints.

Interestingly, the transition challenges Living Labs chose also revealed differences in **normative orientation** that had knock-on effects for implementation. Living Labs with a shared commitment to social values like inclusion and wellbeing were more likely to seek opportunities for co-creation and practical action. These Living Labs often functioned as spaces for **social innovation**. Those that explored **systemically oriented challenges** required more structured multi-actor engagement and experimentation just to make sense of the complex issues involved.

By contrast, Living Labs that focused on more **bounded or technical issues** tended towards controlled implementations that were structured around observation and analysis. Their methods were highly planned, and their work did not significantly change or deviate over time. Here, the methodology was typically implemented in ways that emphasised evidence-based rather than experiential learning.

A similar pattern emerged between Living Labs that grounded their work in explicit conceptual frameworks and those with a lighter theoretical scaffolding, which were usually more flexible in implementation. In practice, most Living Labs sat somewhere between these poles. They took a **pragmatic approach** to implementation, balancing flexibility and adaptation with more structured elements, and developing purposeful relationships without being wholly contingent on co-creation.

As this suggests, implementation often depended on the fit between the Living Lab methodology and the **nature of the transition challenge**. Some challenges, especially involving people-centred issues like food dignity or digital inclusion, aligned more naturally with the participatory aspects of the methodology. Others, like irrigation systems and land-use models, made Living Labs more likely to centre on data experimentation.

6.2. Lessons from collaboration and co-design

Although collaboration and co-design were central to the Living Lab methodology, how these ideals were implemented varied considerably. Some of the most visible differences between Living Labs lie in how they **operationalised collaboration and co-design**. As already noted, some Living Labs developed highly participatory processes. They closely involved stakeholders in the design and delivery of their work, with stakeholders influencing not only the outputs of the Living Lab but also the direction of inquiry. In other Living Labs, stakeholders were more often respondents or consultees than direct co-designers.

Some of these differences stemmed from the focus and orientation of each Living Lab, as discussed above. Yet collaborative approaches were also **highly context dependent**. In some Pilot Regions, **multi-actor collaboration** could be readily achieved. This enabled strong stakeholder engagement and supported shared decision-making. In particular, capable public agencies or strong **intermediary organisations** enabled consistent engagement between partners and

stakeholders and provided sustained support. Pre-existing **cohesion between local actors** also had a strong influence on the feasibility of participatory approaches and network building. In more cohesive contexts, stakeholders could be involved quickly and channels for their participation identified.

In regions where there was **low stakeholder cohesion or capacity**, Living Labs needed more groundwork. In fragmented or lower-trust contexts in particular, Living Labs had to either adapt their collaborative ideals and/or rely more heavily on the Pilot Region Partner's input. These relational differences affected the pace of work and further influenced the kinds of insights and outcomes that Living Labs were able to generate.

As this suggests, **early relationship building was essential** for co-design activities to be meaningful and effective. Generally, partners who could build from prior collaboration or existing networks were able to integrate participation and shared decision-making into their ways of working more quickly. Where relationships were new or trust was lacking, early work was dominated by building rapport and clarifying expectations. For example, the North Karelia (FI) Living Lab needed to gain the trust of immigrant communities, and the team in Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG) spent significant time persuading small producers to participate. Although the groundwork required slowed progress, it was indispensable. These factors meant that **success could hinge on interpersonal dynamics** rather than just methodological design.

The **role of Pilot Region Partners** was particularly important for shaping effective collaboration. Pilot Region Partners who could coordinate participation, translate between stakeholders, and maintain momentum for engagement were central to building trust and enabling progress. Pilot Region Partners that had **strong local legitimacy** were usually better able to convene stakeholders and align the Living Lab's work with relevant strategy or policy decision-making. Where Pilot Region Partners were less able to play these brokerage roles, Living Labs tended to move more slowly, found it harder to build or sustain stakeholder engagement, and placed more reliance on researchers. At the same time, Living Lab Coordinators that were an 'outsider' to the region could bring new perspectives, helping Pilot Region Partners to identify issues that may have been overlooked or taken for granted.

Stakeholder engagement was also influenced by **clarity of purpose**. Many Living Labs found that stakeholders became more actively engaged once they had articulated **concrete goals that were locally meaningful and could offer clear ways to contribute**. While focus was broad or evolving, there was more uncertainty for stakeholders, and participation could appear abstract or burdensome. Even in cases where stakeholders were initially sceptical, engagement improved over time as Living Lab activities produced visible or useful results.

However, participation was **not shaped by willingness alone**. Even when interest was high, some stakeholders, such as rural community groups and small businesses, faced practical constraints that limited their involvement. Living Labs sometimes needed to compensate for this, either by **relying on core groups of committed actors or adapting activities to reduce demands** on participants. More prosaically, Living Labs necessarily operated within RUSTIK's largely fixed project timelines. However, local stakeholders often worked on seasonal, political, or organisational timelines. Misalignments between schedules could create difficulties for engagement. For example, school calendars created constraints for work with young people, and agricultural cycles shaped engagement with land-based stakeholders.

Where collaboration worked well, it often **added value beyond the Living Lab's immediate outputs**. This could include improvements in mutual understanding, stronger networks, new or increased cross-sector collaboration, and improved awareness of how evidence can support local or regional strategies. Overall, RUSTIK's experience demonstrates that collaboration and co-design are **not merely methodological choices but relational processes requiring time, effort, and alignment**.

6.3. Lessons from data experiments

As with implementation and collaboration, data experiments varied according to Living Labs' contexts and the capabilities they could access. These differences reflected both differing levels of **technical capability and analytical experience** and the practical **feasibility of accessing or generating relevant data** for the Pilot Region. Consequently, some Living Labs were able to trial innovative tools or work with multiple datasets and complex analytical methods, while others pursued simpler, more exploratory approaches aimed at improving basic data availability or building foundational evidence about the transition challenge.

Technical capacity and skills within the Living Lab inevitably shaped how data experiments could proceed. Unsurprisingly, partners who had existing data expertise or identified how to gain relevant further capacity were better able to develop ambitious experiments. Limited capacities meant that some experiments necessarily centred on more basic or conventional approaches. There were a few cases where 'experimentation' merely replicated familiar methods and entrenched disciplinary ways of working. In most cases, however, **improved skills** were reported in areas such as data literacy, visualisation, GIS techniques, survey design, and mixed methods integration.

Within the Pilot Region, **data maturity** was similarly decisive. In regions where relevant data was – or could readily be made – available and accessible, Living Labs were able to explore opportunities for integrating multiple data sources and developing new tools and models. However, Cycle 1 identified widespread uncertainty about what relevant data existed, how to access it, and how reliable or comparable it was. The data experiments confirmed that **structural limitations in data** shaped what was possible in practice. Several Living Labs found that there was an immediate need to establish baseline information or locate and consolidate fragmented data sources, requiring significant effort. Others found that inconsistencies in or between datasets, outdated data, and a lack of granular spatial data significantly limited opportunities for analysis. In low data contexts, experimentation often turned towards **primary data collection**. Consequently, several data experiments focused on **foundational evidence-building** rather than cutting-edge data innovation. These experiments nevertheless frequently delivered valuable **capacity-building outcomes**, such as sharing data practices that were new to stakeholders or building awareness of relevant evidence.

As this suggests, **even modest initiatives could unlock useful new insights**. Experiments that integrated datasets, combined qualitative or quantitative evidence, or visualised information more clearly often proved especially valuable for stakeholders. For example, mapping small rural businesses in Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT) helped reveal the extent of these businesses and their sectoral structures, leading to increased recognition of their local importance. Such cases show that adding value in rural data contexts may lie less in technical novelty than in **making relevant information legible and actionable**.

Data experiments were most effective when closely **aligned to concrete policy or practice needs**. Experiments that directly linked to strategy or policy needs tended to attract higher levels of stakeholder engagement and have clearer routes for the uptake of results. Experiments that were less embedded within an institutional agenda generated insights but struggled to connect results to decision-making.

Beyond Pilot Regions themselves, the **potential for scaling or replication** varied across data experiments. Some Living Labs developed methods or tools, such as Gloucestershire's (UK) dynamic dashboard and Galicia's (ES) decision support tool, that could be adapted for other regions. This transfer appears to have higher potential where data sources were standardised or available at a larger scale, and where the techniques used are replicable. Other Living Labs developed more tailored and context-dependent approaches that provided local value but have more limited applicability. These differences illustrate the different potential impact pathways that emerge from place-based experimentation pathways, in which there is an inevitable **trade-off between specificity and transferability**.

In general, data experiments served to **highlight pervasive data gaps and uneven data infrastructures** pertaining to rural areas. Overall, diverse experimentation demonstrated that the methodology was flexible enough to accommodate both incremental and more innovative approaches to rural data generation. This reinforced the value of data experiments as a **diagnostic activity**, revealing the practical conditions needed for more complex and innovative approaches in future. Practical learning from data experiments will be covered in more detail in *Deliverable 5.2*, forthcoming.

6.4. Lessons from sustainability and legacy planning

Sustaining outcomes beyond the RUSTIK project period emerged as a shared aspiration for most Living Labs. There are several areas where Living Labs have the potential to leave a longer-term legacy, but realising this is likely to require active planning. We reflect on the need and potential for planning in this section; however, we note that, given the timeline of the project, many of the longer-term impacts of the Living Labs' work will not have been captured in our reflections on the operational Cycles.

First, **long-term collaborative relationships** offer a valuable legacy for Living Labs, but the potential is uneven in practice. Partners and reports frequently mentioned that Living Labs had strengthened networks, and these links were seen as building mutual understanding and providing potential for future joint initiatives. However, maintaining relationships requires ongoing effort and institutional support, and there is a need for future collaborative opportunities to incentivise this. Where such opportunities may be scarce, relationships risk dissipating over time.

The durability of data-related outputs will depend on **stewardship**. Many Living Labs have produced new or improved datasets or tools that offer future value. However, partners themselves have concerns about how to maintain and update these assets over time. Without viable arrangements for ongoing management, including resourcing, the value created by data experiments may diminish as data become outdated or tools fall out of use.

Fortunately, **sustainability appears strongest where experiments were well-aligned** with existing organisational responsibilities and data needs. Tools and data that can be integrated into

initiatives and workflows are more likely to support governance tasks and strategic planning processes, and vice versa. There is greater uncertainty around tools and data that require new mandates or significant coordination and technical capacity. This underscores the importance of **embedding data within organisations rather than solely within projects**.

Importantly in this context, however, **external conditions** beyond partners' control are likely to play a major role in determining the legacy of Living Labs. Shifting political priorities and changes in staff, leadership, or budgets can all pose risks to achieving and sustaining outcomes over time. Even strong relationships and well-designed tools may struggle if policy agendas move on or organisations face future resource constraints.

Overall, sustaining outcomes from Living Labs after RUSTIK concludes will likely require **realistic and managed expectations**. Despite the hopes seen in the literature (see Section 2) for Living Labs and experimentation to catalyse transformative change, Living Labs cannot by themselves resolve longstanding structural challenges – a point that is particularly salient for rural areas.

Instead, it may be more pragmatic to conceptualise the legacy of Living Labs as building foundations that *could* support longer-term outcomes if supported by appropriate investment and institutional commitment. Although partners expressed the potential for transformative change to occur through implementing the methodology, it was agreed that the work of the Living Labs during the operational cycles prepared the foundations for such change, without completely delivering it. The challenges highlighted in Section 5.2.4, such as internal dynamics and structural constraints, all have implications for the extent of the changes that have occurred throughout the project. However, as one academic partner reflected: *“The project has introduced meaningful change. Although these changes may not yet constitute structural transformation, they represent progressive shifts that lay the foundation for more robust strategic orientations in the medium and long term”*.

6.5. Living Lab implementation typology

Drawing from observations from previous studies (Voytenko et al. 2016, Sengers et al. 2019, Bulkeley et al. 2018) and reflections from RUSTIK, three sets of dimensions can be identified that help to explain the different ways each Living Lab operated:

1. **Implementation dimensions** concern how the Living Lab approach was implemented through a specific place-based methodology in practice. They capture the degree of co-creation and the balance between structure and emergence. They define the form of the Living Lab as it unfolded.
2. **Contextual dimensions** describe the structural, institutional, and relational conditions in which each Living Lab operated. They were not part of the methodology itself but strongly shaped what was feasible.
3. **Conceptual dimensions** describe the intellectual positioning of each Living Lab. These shape how challenges are framed and the theoretical or analytical stance of the work. They influence strategic choices rather than technical feasibility.

Table 10 outlines the specific dimensions within these groups that influenced how RUSTIK Living Labs operated in practice.

Table 10: Implementation, contextual, and conceptual dimensions of RUSTIK Living Lab operationalisation

Type	Dimension	Description
Implementation dimensions	Operationalisation	The extent to which the Living Lab incorporated core principles of co-creation and participation, real-world experimentation, and iteration and learning.
	Partnerships and roles	How responsibilities, leadership and decision-making were distributed between partners, and the extent to which stakeholders were engaged.
	Intervention vs observation	The extent to which the Living Lab actively sought to change practice or was more focused on building observational understanding.
	Control vs contingency	The degree to which implementation followed a pre-planned design versus evolving dynamically in response to external factors.
Contextual dimensions	Institutional capacity	The capability, stability, and continuity of the institutions involved.
	Data maturity	The availability, quality, interoperability, and accessibility of relevant data, and the technical competence to use it.
	Local actor cohesion	The strength of local networks, including trust and shared objectives.
	Normative orientation	How explicitly values-led or mission-driven the Living Lab was.
Conceptual dimensions	Challenge nature	The extent to which the challenge addressed was systemic and complex, or more specific, technical, or bounded.
	Theoretical and analytical emphasis	How strongly the Living Lab drew on conceptual frameworks or analytical models to structure the experiment design or interpretation.

Based on these dimensions, four implementation clusters emerge from across RUSTIK’s fourteen Living Labs. These reflect distinct combinations of how Living Labs were configured and conducted their experiments and navigated their contextual environments. Rather than forcing RUSTIK’s diverse Living Labs into rigid categories, the clusters should be read as ideal types representing the patterns that recur most consistently across cases.

6.5.1. Participatory change-makers

Living Labs in this cluster demonstrated strong co-creation and regular iteration. For these Living Labs, the methodology went beyond being a structured engagement process and became a **vehicle for social and organisational innovation**. They were shaped by **strong local networks** and actors who enabled experimentation and took **shared ownership of outcomes**. Their key characteristics were:

- Strong normative or human-centred framing around shared values.
- High operationalisation of the principles of co-creation, iteration, and real-world testing, with methods evolving responsively.
- Shared leadership between research and practice partners, with the Pilot Region Partner playing a catalysing role.
- An interventionist mode, pursuing actions aimed at directly changing practices, services, or governance processes.
- Relational conditions where high levels of trust and stakeholder collaboration allowed for more experimentation.

Examples: Osona (ES) developed a Quality-of-Life index as a co-created planning tool. Stakeholders actively shaped data collection priorities, and findings fed directly into local renewal decisions. Leadership was genuinely shared between the municipality and research partners. Gloucestershire (UK) had strong trust with local voluntary and community sector organisations, which enabled the co-design of a community-friendly smart dashboard. The project aimed to change how local actors could access and interpret data, rather than just analyse existing conditions. Iteration was driven by stakeholder feedback.

6.5.2. Applied experimenters

These Living Labs were characterised by a **strong technical or analytical emphasis**, typically supported by **mature data and high institutional capacity**. They implemented the methodology in structured and controlled ways, with less direct co-creation than the participatory change-makers. They illustrate how Living Labs can function to support evidence-based policy decision-making by producing new analytical insights. Their key characteristics were:

- A framing around systemic challenges, especially concerning environmental governance.
- An operationalisation of the Living Lab approach as a framework for applied analysis.
- Structured partnership roles, with the Pilot Region Partner providing strategic guidance or access.
- Experimentation centred on more complex analysis, such as modelling, spatial analysis, and data integration.
- Adherence to predefined methods and timelines.
- High data maturity in the region enabled more ambitious data designs.

Examples: Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara (IT) implemented a technically demanding data experiment integrating multiple data sources on irrigation and water use. Data on this topic had considerable implications for future climate and environmental resilience strategies. The core experiment was analytically focused, with structured focus groups validating outputs. Galicia (ES) developed a decision support system as part of a key regional land use planning initiative. The Living Lab functioned as an applied analytical platform for regional authorities, emphasising robustness testing and sensitivity analysis.

6.5.3. Evidence sharers

This cluster reflects Living Labs where implementation was practical, purposeful and engaged. They were primarily concerned with **understanding local systems, generating evidence, and building knowledge** among stakeholders, rather than designing or testing new data-driven innovations. They reflect a pragmatic mode of experimentation, with an emphasis on **improving understanding and supporting future decision-making**. Their key characteristics were:

- A focus on addressing meaningful local challenges.
- Incorporating Living Lab principles with a researcher-led design.
- Functional partnerships with stakeholders who were engaged and supporting but not strongly involved in co-design.
- A generally stable methodological approach, with some adaptation and iteration.
- An observational mode, with work focused on diagnosis and evidence-building and limited direct intervention.
- Moderate institutional capacity and actor cohesion, creating space for collaboration but also placing some constraints on ambition.

Examples: Rhein-Hunsrück (DE) focused on diagnosing labour market mismatches through large-scale surveys of young people and employers. Stakeholders were engaged through dialogue events and dissemination activities, with the Living Lab's analysis aiming to build shared understanding rather than directly intervene. Mazowieckie (PL) catalysed dialogue with entrepreneurs about local development potential. The Living Lab prioritised mutual learning, using workshops to share and interpret findings and spark ideas.

6.5.4. Foundation builders

This cluster represents Living Labs operating in lower capacity, low-data, or fragmented relational contexts, where the methodology was adapted into a more **foundational or capacity-building platform**. These Living Labs confronted constraints that limited the feasibility of either participatory co-creation or technical experimentation. Instead, they worked to lay the **groundwork for future intervention** by strengthening data and/or networks. Their key characteristics were:

- An interest in broadly defined transition challenges.
- Difficulties implementing some elements of the Living Lab methodology due to contextual limitations.
- More contingent implementation, with conditions and circumstances leading to changed plans.
- An observational mode, with emphasis on mapping needs, revealing gaps, and building baseline data.
- Low data maturity and/or actor cohesion, requiring more emphasis on capacity-building efforts.

Examples: Zaječar (RS) operated in a low-data and low-trust context, and prioritised building basic local data infrastructure and skills. Hybrid methods and face-to-face engagement were necessary to build participation. Baseline evidence and enhanced institutional capacity were key outcomes. Świętokrzyskie (PL) operated in a context of limited local data, specifically on rural tourism. Living Lab activities focused on building baseline evidence through surveys, interviews, mapping, and local inventories. Stakeholder engagement centred on validation and dissemination.

These typologies are designed to offer a starting point for the analysis of results and outcomes, which will be presented in D5.1.

6.6. Theory of Change for RUSTIK Living Labs

The Theory of Change (ToC) approach (Weiss 1995) is used to “surface and articulate” (Connell & Kubisch 1998: 1) the logical steps and underlying assumptions that connect activities to anticipated outcomes. It belongs to a wider family of theory-based approaches for examining intervention logic and pathways to change. In short, a ToC is based on a set of activities that, under certain assumptions and conditions, are expected to lead towards the achievement of tangible objectives and, in turn, contribute to intermediate and longer-term outcomes.

Drawing on the RUSTIK Living Lab methodology and the lessons from implementation discussed above, a ToC has been developed at the level of RUSTIK Living Labs as a whole. This programme level ToC consolidates the shared logic through which Living Labs operated in practice. It reflects learning from implementation rather than being a pre-defined model and is informed by observed variation between the Living Labs. While the ToC focuses on Living Labs as they were implemented in RUSTIK, it also synthesises learning that is relevant for future Living Labs in rural development.

It should be noted that each Living Lab developed its own context-specific ToC during Cycle 2 as part of articulating its Pilot Region’s transition narrative. These individual ToCs reflect local priorities, actors, and governance conditions. They are described separately in D3.2 and will also be analysed in D4.3.

The following sub-sections outline the main components of each part of the programme-level ToC for Living Labs, which can be viewed in Appendix B: Theory of Change diagram.

6.6.1. Inputs

Inputs refer to the methodological, financial, organisational, relational, and contextual resources that enabled RUSTIK Living Labs to be established and to operate across diverse Pilot Regions. At the programme level, these inputs describe the enabling environment in which Living Labs were expected to operate. They were:

- **RUSTIK Living Lab methodology:** providing a structured approach and common principles while allowing flexibility in local implementation.
- **Project budget:** dedicated financial resources to support Living Lab coordination and activities, and cross-project learning between Pilot Regions. In RUSTIK, both the Living Lab Coordinator and Pilot Region Partner had independent budget lines for implementing the Living Lab.
- **Living Lab Coordinator:** research capacity in each Living Lab, responsible for methodological design, data work, facilitation, and linking activities to wider project objectives.
- **Pilot Region Partner:** a locally embedded practice partner providing knowledge, legitimacy, stakeholder access, and pathways to policy within the Pilot Region.
- **Work Package Coordination:** central support for Living Labs within RUSTIK, ensuring methodological coherence, quality assurance, peer learning, and alignment with wider project objectives.
- **Engaged stakeholders:** providing time, knowledge, and trust to the Living Lab.

- **Institutional and policy contexts:** governance arrangements, strategies, and capacities within the Pilot Region, shaping the scope for experimentation and the uptake of Living Lab outcomes.
- **Data infrastructure and access:** availability of relevant data sources and analytical tools, including both local datasets and the RUSTIK data viewer.

6.6.2. Activities

Activities refer to the structured and iterative actions through which Living Lab inputs were used in practice. These capture both the operational processes required to run Living Labs and the experimental and participatory practices that enabled them to respond to local contexts. They are:

- **Initiation, leadership, and coordination:** establishing Living Labs, clarifying roles and responsibilities, and providing ongoing facilitation and coordination
- **Stakeholder engagement and relationship-building:** identifying, convening, and sustaining engagement with relevant local and regional actors, including managing expectations and tensions.
- **Context analysis and problem framing:** developing a shared understanding of local conditions, institutional settings, and transition challenges.
- **Envisioning and co-designing:** jointly defining Living Lab goals and tasks through collaborative planning processes.
- **Data collection, integration, and analysis:** designing and implementing the data experiment, including gathering and analysing relevant data.
- **Iterative adaptation:** refining goals and activities in response to emerging learning and contextual constraints and opportunities.
- **Evaluation and reflection:** assessing progress, outcomes, and ways of working through feedback loops and shared reflection within and across Living Labs.
- **Communication and knowledge transfer:** communicating findings and translating insights into formats usable for policy and practice both within the Pilot Region and at wider levels.
- **Co-producing conclusions:** synthesising learning into conclusions and recommendations to inform future action beyond the project.

6.6.3. Objectives

Objectives articulate the intended directions of change that Living Labs sought to influence. They reflect what RUSTIK's Living Lab methodology aimed to enable or strengthen through the activities above. They are:

1. **Strengthen multi-actor collaboration and territorial networks:** to foster sustained collaboration among actors within Pilot Regions.
2. **Build data capabilities and skills:** to enhance the capacity of local and regional actors to design, use, and reflect on data, evidence, and experimental approaches.
3. **Improve place-based practice and institutional learning:** to support changes in how organisations understand, design, and implement place-based interventions and rural development practices.
4. **Generate new data, methods, tools, and evidence through experimentation:** to produce relevant data, analytical methods, tools, and insights tailored to rural transition challenges within Pilot Regions.

5. **Enhance policy knowledge and innovation across governance levels:** to inform and support regional and multi-level policy learning.
6. **Provide actionable evidence and tools for local actors:** to increase awareness and practical use of evidence, tools, and insights among local rural stakeholders.
7. **Lay foundations for sustained use and uptake beyond the project:** to support the embedding, transfer, or scaling of Living Lab approaches, tools, and learning.
8. **Advance academic and methodological knowledge on Living Labs and rural transitions:** to contribute to research knowledge, methodological development, and future research agendas beyond the project.

6.6.4. Outcomes

Outcomes describe the changes that are expected to emerge as a result of the Living Lab activities and the achievement of objectives. The ToC distinguishes between short-term, mid-term, and longer-term outcomes to reflect immediate changes in capacities and practices and more gradual shifts in behaviour, policy, and knowledge uptake.

Short-term outcomes are those that are expected to occur within the project. **Mid-term outcomes** are changes in practice, organisational behaviours, and decision-making processes that are expected to emerge after initial Living Lab activities, as actors begin to apply learning and mobilise relationships developed during the project. **Longer-term outcomes** may emerge in future, as learning, relationships, and practices from the Living Labs are taken up, adapted, or scaled by actors and institutions. These outcomes sit beyond RUSTIK’s direct accountability ceiling. That is, while RUSTIK seeks to influence the conditions under which longer-term outcomes could occur, their realisation depends on external factors outside Living Labs’ control.

Table 11: Intended outcomes for Living Labs

Outcome	Description
Short-term outcomes	
New and strengthened relationships and territorial networks	Development of new connections and enhancement of existing relationships among local, regional, and research actors.
Shared understanding of local contexts and transition challenges	Greater alignment among Living Lab partners and stakeholders around key challenges and opportunities within each Pilot Region.
Increased awareness of local conditions and dynamics	Improved understanding among partners and stakeholders of rural conditions, evidence about transition challenges, and the potential pathways for action that these lead to.
Improved data literacy and confidence in using evidence	Enhanced ability and confidence among participants to interpret and apply data to rural transition challenges.
Increased empowerment and agency through co-creation	Greater sense of ownership and improved confidence among stakeholders resulting from involvement in co-designed activities.

Outcome	Description
Enhanced readiness for further action	Improved preparedness of organisations and networks to pursue follow-up activities, new initiatives, or policy ideas beyond the project.
Mid-term outcomes	
Improved coordination across actors, contexts, and tools	More effective mechanisms for coordinating diverse actors, within and between different territorial contexts, and for applying data and policy tools.
Enhanced territorial knowledge and evidence use	Deeper, more integrated understanding of local and regional dynamics, supported by improved use of data, analysis, and contextual knowledge.
Embedding of learning into organisational practices	Incorporation of Living Lab methods and insights into organisational routines and strategies.
Incremental changes in policy thinking and practice	Early shifts in policy framing, priorities, mechanisms, or implementation at local or regional levels.
Availability and uptake of new knowledge and tools for rural development	Use of co-produced knowledge and tools by policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and local actors.
Advancement of research approaches and methodologies	Development and application refined methodological approaches for Living Labs in rural development, and of novel data, methods, and analytical techniques.
Longer-term outcomes	
Contributions to socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital transitions in rural areas	Learning from Living Labs informs improved responses to transition challenges.
Strengthened mechanisms for multi-level and multi-territorial governance	Improved alignment and coordination between local, regional, national, and European policy actors supporting effective decision-making in rural development.
Improved integration of place-based evidence into policy frameworks	Greater incorporation of granular data and analysis into multi-level policy design and implementation.
Positive spillover effects in local and regional development practice	Diffusion of learning, methods, and tools beyond the Pilot Regions to other regions and rural areas.
Influence on future research agendas and programme design	Uptake of both Living Lab approaches and the learning generated in subsequent rural research and funding calls.

6.6.5. Assumptions

Evidently, the ToC rests on assumptions, which describe the conditions that are expected to hold for Living Lab activities to contribute to the intended objectives and outcomes.

Assumptions sit outside direct control, but influence whether and how Living Labs can function as intended. Making these assumptions explicit, therefore, helps to clarify the scope of the Living Lab methodology and recognise dependencies. These are:

- **Transitions are understood as relevant to rural development:** it is assumed that the socio-economic and demographic, climate and environmental, and digital transitions RUSTIK focuses on are recognised as presenting meaningful challenges and opportunities within Pilot Regions.
- **Political and institutional willingness to engage with rural transitions exists:** it is assumed that there is sufficient political interest and institutional openness at local and regional levels to engage with rural transition challenges and support Living Lab activity.
- **Core partners have the capacity to participate effectively:** it is assumed that academic institutions and Pilot Region Partner organisations have sufficient staff time and appropriate skills and capacity to establish Living Labs and support their activities.
- **Local contexts are recognised:** it is assumed that actors acknowledge that rural areas differ in their functions, contexts, and characteristics, and that these differences matter for designing interventions.
- **Preparatory and co-design work is valued:** it is assumed that there is shared recognition of the importance of preparatory work and co-design in developing relevant, legitimate, and effective Living Lab activities.
- **Iteration and adaptation are accepted as legitimate ways of working:** it is assumed that Living Lab participants accept adaptation and learning over time as integral to the approach rather than as negative signs of failure.
- **Participants are open to experimentation and uncertainty:** it is assumed that core Living Lab participants are willing to work in experimental conditions, including dealing with uncertainty and learning from partial or unexpected results.
- **Learning and reflection are actively prioritised:** it is assumed that Living Lab results are critically discussed, limitations are acknowledged, and learning is intentionally sought from both successes and difficulties.
- **Stakeholders are willing and able to engage:** it is assumed that relevant stakeholders are willing to invest time and share knowledge, and are not structurally excluded from participating in the Living Lab.
- **Relevant data can be accessed and evidence generated:** it is assumed that data required to support experimentation are available and can be accessed, and can be used to generate evidence in ways that are meaningful for the Living Lab.
- **Learning can be translated into policy or practice:** it is assumed that there are plausible pathways through which Living Lab insights can inform organisational practices, future interventions, and policy decision-making.
- **External conditions do not fundamentally undermine Living Lab activities:** while change and uncertainty are expected, it is assumed that wider political, institutional, and economic conditions remain sufficiently stable to allow Living Lab activities to proceed.

6.6.6. Risks

Risks may affect the ability of Living Lab activities to contribute to the intended objectives and outcomes. Table 12 groups these into contextual, operational, methodological, and knowledge-related risks to reflect the different ways in which Living Lab processes may be constrained or disrupted.

Table 12: Risks for RUSTIK Living Labs

Risk	Potential impact
Contextual risks	
Limited political or policy interest in rural transitions	A lack of political attention or sensitivity to rural issues may reduce institutional support for Living Lab activities and limit engagement with their results.
Place-blind or top-down approaches to intervention design	Failure to recognise place-specific transition pathways may lead to generic or inappropriate interventions that do not reflect local needs or dynamics.
External political, institutional, or economic shocks	Changes beyond the control of the project (e.g. political turnover, organisational restructuring, economic pressures) may disrupt Living Lab processes or priorities.
Operational risks	
Insufficient organisational capacity and resources	Limited availability of staff time, skills, or financial resources may constrain collaboration or the sustained operation of Living Labs.
Stakeholder fatigue or uneven participation	Stakeholders may lack time, incentives, or trust to engage meaningfully, leading to partial, unrepresentative, or declining participation over time.
Misalignment between Living Labs and policy or organisational timelines	Differences between Living Lab cycles and decision-making or funding timelines may limit participation or the uptake of findings.
Methodological risks	
Weak or rushed preparatory work and co-design	Insufficient time or attention to preparation and co-design may result in misaligned activities or reduced innovation within Living Lab experiments.
Resistance to experimentation and uncertainty	Reliance on established methods or reluctance to engage with uncertainty may undermine the experimental and exploratory nature of the Living Lab approach.
Limited sensitivity to local dynamics within Living Lab teams	A lack of contextual understanding or appropriate attitudes among participants may weaken trust, relevance, and collaboration.
Knowledge-related risks	
Limited availability or accessibility of relevant data	Gaps in data availability, access restrictions, or poor data quality may constrain analysis and evidence-informed learning.

Risk	Potential impact
Misinterpretation or incomplete use of evidence and learning	Insufficient reflection or analytical capacity may lead to misunderstanding of results, limitations, or implications.
Ineffective communication and dissemination of results	Failure to identify appropriate audiences or use suitable formats and channels may limit awareness, uptake, and longer-term influence.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

This section draws together the main conclusions of the report and sets out their implications for future rural Living Lab design and implementation.

This report has provided a grounded synthesis of how RUSTIK Living Labs functioned in practice across diverse rural contexts. Using existing literature, it has demonstrated the rationale for using Living Labs in RUSTIK, presented the cyclical nature of their operationalisation, and illustrated how the Living Labs were supported in developing data experiments to address their chosen transition challenges.

To examine the implementation of the Living Labs, the report drew on several key Deliverables regarding Living Labs' key features, data needs, and their reports from Cycle 1 and Cycle 2, in addition to semi-structured interviews with partners, to explore the methodology's implementation. The final results from Living Labs' data experiments, and their implications for data use for rural transitions, will be analysed in D5.1 and D5.2. (see Figure 4 for the links between Work Packages and associated Deliverables).

After the project ends, we envisage continued reciprocal relationships between the work completed in these WPs, with the conclusions of WP5 continuing to conceptually reinforce WP1, WP2 and WP4.

Figure 4: The relationship between the RUSTIK Work Packages, the Deliverables used to inform this report, and the WP5 Deliverables that will report on the final Living Lab results

7.1. Key findings

Rather than treating Living Labs as a single, transferable model for place-based innovation, the synthesis demonstrates how the form and function of RUSTIK's fourteen Living Labs were influenced by institutional capacities, stakeholder cohesion, data maturity, and governance arrangements in rural areas. Although their implementation experiences were unique, an analysis using the three dimensions in Section 6.5 shows areas of commonality across the fourteen Living Labs. These clusters represent patterns that recurred most consistently across cases and should not be read as ideal types, but as a framework that may be useful for assessing future Living Lab implementation. The Theory of Change that follows in Section 6.6. consolidates the shared logic through which the Living Labs operated and synthesises learning that can inform future Living Lab implementation for rural development.

Overall, learning from RUSTIK contributes three key insights to knowledge on rural Living Labs and data innovation:

- **Rural Living Labs as diagnostic and capacity-building platforms.**
RUSTIK's experience shows that, in rural contexts, Living Labs may function less as mechanisms for rapid innovation and more as platforms for diagnosing challenges and building capacities. Their value lies in helping local actors explore and frame concrete challenges, recognise constraints, and identify the forms of practical action that are feasible within existing conditions.
- **Data experiments as foundational rather than transformative.**
Across RUSTIK's Living Labs, data experiments were most effective when they improved the accessibility and usability of relevant data. Building these foundations did not necessarily require technically ambitious solutions. Often, data experiments were able to make meaningful contributions by consolidating fragmented information, supporting shared interpretation, and building confidence in evidence use.
- **Intermediary roles as a structural condition.**
Intermediary actors played a crucial role in RUSTIK Living Labs by convening stakeholders and sustaining engagement with them over time and by translating evidence into usable forms. These brokerage functions emerge as a necessary structural condition for Living Labs in rural governance settings, rather than as a matter of individual skill or good practice alone.

These insights underline the importance of aligning expectations for Living Labs with rural contexts and provide a basis for more realistic and effective future design.

7.2. Recommendations for future rural Living Labs

The experience of implementing Living Labs across fourteen diverse rural regions raises broader implications for the future design of place-based, multi-actor rural development and innovation processes. These recommendations highlight both the potential value of the Living Lab approach and the conditions needed for it to function effectively in rural policy settings.

1. **Design Living Labs around governance entry points, not project timelines.**

Living Labs are more likely to influence decision-making when they are aligned with existing governance cycles, such as strategy development or funding programming, and governance scales. Future initiatives should identify where and when Living Lab activities and outputs are able to feed into these processes, rather than designing Living Labs as parallel projects.

2. Match ambition to capacity and allow for incremental progress.

Time, skills, institutional stability, and organisational resources vary across rural actors and should shape both expectations for Living Labs and design choices. Living Labs should be designed to allow sufficient time for relationship-building (particularly in lower-capacity or fragmented stakeholder contexts), reduce participation burdens, and recognise incremental achievements rather than expect rapid transformation.

3. Prioritise foundational experimentation and ‘low regret’ actions.

In many rural areas, the most valuable outcomes from Living Labs are likely to arise from clarifying challenges and identifying feasible, low-cost interventions that can be pursued regardless of political or funding changes. Treating such foundational work as a legitimate outcome can help build future readiness for more ambitious innovation.

4. Resource intermediary roles as a core component of Living Lab design.

Effective Living Labs depend on trusted intermediary actors who can convene stakeholders and translate learning. Intermediaries also have a key role in stewarding outputs over time. These brokerage functions should be explicitly planned and appropriately resourced. They should not be assumed to emerge organically or be provided voluntarily.

5. Plan for sustainability and stewardship from the outset.

Living Labs can produce outputs (like RUSTIK’s data experiments) with potential long-term value but uncertain longevity. Future Living Labs should establish early clarity on stewardship responsibilities and regularly revisit the potential pathways to longer-term sustainability and the practical actions these require.

6. Build in structured opportunities for reflection and learning.

Although ‘learning by doing’ is a celebrated part of the Living Lab methodology, Living Labs in practice are most effective when learning is made explicit rather than assumed. Future implementations should include time and structured mechanisms for collective reflection on what worked, what did not, and why, to support both ongoing adaptation and the development of practical insights.

The findings and recommendations presented in this report reinforce the value and potential of Living Labs as adaptive, place-based approaches for supporting mutual learning and practical action in rural development contexts. The RUSTIK experience shows how Living Labs can be configured in different ways to respond to local contexts and support governance needs. As rural areas continue to navigate complex transitions, the insights from RUSTIK highlight the importance of collaborative, context-sensitive approaches with realistic ambitions. They also served to highlight multiple, persistent, and particular structural rural challenges.

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Appendix A: Interview guide

The following semi-structured interview guide was used in the interviews with 27 partners, reported in Section 5.

Opening framing

Aim: establish context and comfort.

1. Can you briefly describe your role in your Living Lab?
2. Prior to RUSTIK, had you had any experience with Living Labs?
 - a. Follow up: Remembering back to the start of RUSTIK, what were your initial impressions about working in a Living Lab?
 - b. Prompt: Were they confused? Looking forward to it? Did they have expectations?
3. From your perspective now, what does the Living Lab methodology mean in practice?
 - a. Prompt: How would you explain the Living Lab methodology to someone new to it?
 - b. Probe: How do they understand the Living Lab methodology to have been implemented in their Pilot Region?

Methodological functionality and practice

Aim: reflect on how the methodology worked in practical terms.

4. Overall, how suitable and useful did you find the Living Lab way of working in your Pilot Region?
5. To what extent was the Living Lab approach relevant for your transition challenge context?
 - a. Probe: Was it helpful for recognising and discussing the transition challenge/s in your region?
6. How did the co-design process work in practice?
 - a. Prompt: What was straightforward? Where were there frictions? How did they find working with an academic partner (if practice), or a practice partner (if academic)?
7. What challenges or limitations did you encounter in implementing the Living Lab methodology?

Differences made, outcomes and impact

Focus: how has the LL as a methodology supported outcomes? What was the added value of the methodology?

8. In comparison to other projects you have worked on, what, if anything, did you do – or do differently – because of the Living Lab approach?
 - a. Probe: If they did not do anything differently, why not?
 - b. Follow up: If you imagine RUSTIK work in your Pilot Region without the Living Lab approach, what, if anything, would be missing?
 - c. Probe: If nothing comes up, why do they think that is?
9. Is there anything new that exists because of the Living Lab? If so, what?

- a. Prompt: relationships, ideas, data, initiatives, tools, knowledge.
 - b. Probe: If nothing comes up, why do they think that is?
 - c. Follow up: What helped to enable this?
- 10.** To what extent has work in your Living Lab been translated into either concrete interventions or advocacy for improved policies?
- a. Probe: If yes, what enabled this? If not, what hindered this?
 - b. Follow up: What, if any, possibilities can you see for the work you have done to lead to new interventions or policies in the future?
- 11.** To what extent do you think that the data or methods from your data experiment will be used beyond RUSTIK?
- a. Follow up: to what extent do you think that the Living Lab way of working has influenced the use or uptake of data?
- 12.** Were there hopes among the partners for the Living Lab or things you would have liked to achieve that did not work out? If so, what?
- a. Follow up: What hindered this?

Reflection and close

- 13.** If you were to go back and set up the Living Lab all over again, what would you change?
- 14.** Would you use the Living Lab approach again in other rural development projects?
- a. Probe: If so, why? If not, why not?
- 15.** Is there anything else you would like to share about your Living Lab experience?

Appendix B: Theory of Change diagram

